

CoordiNation and Deferral of Bengali Nation- Consciousness: Ishwarchandra Gupta in Nineteenth Century Kolkata

Tamal Dasgupta

Abstract: This paper argues that the course of the development of nation-consciousness in nineteenth century Kolkata as observed in the works of Ishwarchandra Gupta continues to get deflected, owing to the pressure of colonialism and the tendency of Bengali comprador classes to remain supplicant in front of imperialism. In order to describe the structure of Gupta's nationalist project, the word coordiNation is coined. This paper explores how Bengali nation-consciousness is both coordiNated and deferred in the nineteenth century Kolkata that Gupta inhabits.

Keywords: Ishwar Gupta, Nineteenth Century Kolkata, Bengali Nation-Consciousness, Nationalism, *Shongbād Probhākor*, *Kobigān*, *Kobiwala/Kobiyal*, *Pānchāli*, *Toppa*, *Ākhrāi*, *half- Ākhrāi*, Bharatchandra Ray, Ramprasad Sen, Ramnidhi Gupta, Gonjla Guin, Ram Basu, Dashu Ray, Horu Thakur, Bhola Moyra, Anthony Firingi, Rupchand Pokkhi, Ishwarchandra Vidyasagar, Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay, Dinabandhu Mitra, Krishnakamal Bhattacharya.

Our past is a resource that we constantly need to raid in order to illuminate our present, and this is one of the reasons why I embarked on this work. This paper positions Ishwar Gupta within the historical trajectory of nineteenth century Kolkata. While working on Ishwar Gupta – pronounced Ishshor Goopto; I use the spelling Ishwarchandra Gupta throughout this article for familiarity's sake, though Issurchunder Goopto was how he and his contemporaries spelt his name in English, while *Probhakur* was the standard spelling for the name of his newspaper, as we get to know from his *Collected Works* (2: 4) – there was an irresistible temptation to discover in Gupta a precursor/forerunner of the nationalist movement. Indeed as the mentor of Bankim and other nationalist writers like Rangalal Bandyopadhyay and

Dinabandhu Mitra, and having himself pioneered in authoring a number of nationalist poems and having initiated nationalist projects, Ishwarchandra Gupta is entitled to that honour. But this article will not do that. He was not to the nationalist movement and Hindu revival in Bengal what Blake was to the Romantic movement. For one thing, the Hindu revival of Bengal should be best thought of as a Long Revolution (a la Raymond Williams), which started as a resistance movement right after the Mohammedan conquest and reached its apogee at the time of Chaitanya. When Durga Pujo was being reintroduced after the fall of Siraj, at the behest of Krishnachandra of Nadia and Nabakrishna of Kolkata, we witness another milestone in that trajectory. Ishwar Gupta is part of that same trajectory which will see the advent of Bankim afterwards. The first half of nineteenth century, which was the *old* nineteenth century, was culturally dominated by Ishwarchandra (died 1859), and as that former half gave way, gave birth to the later half of nineteenth century, which was to be the *new* nineteenth century, Bankim came to assume that role of the cultural patriarch. However, though both Ishwarchandra and Bankim worked towards building a process of nation-consciousness, the process itself remained very deeply problematic; it always presupposed a surrender of Bengal to the British. It was with the gold from the loot of Bengal that England had its industrial revolution, but Bengalis were too happy for having been free from the shackles of Islamic rule to notice that. Bengal's Hindu revival thus got inextricably, intricately entangled with Bengal's colonisation by the West. What followed was a dialectic of collaboration and confrontation with the west which earmarked the project of Ishwar Gupta and characterised the course of history in nineteenth century Kolkata.

What did this collaboration entail? I suggest that it involved a hermeneutic damage. Let us take an example. In a supposedly neutral, objective description of the interiors of a house, Bankim uses the omniscient narratorial mode to take a potshot at the superstition of Bengali idolatry, decrying Durga and Kali, in his first novel written in English, *Rajmohan's Wife*: “Two paintings of the largest size, from one of which glowered the grim black figure of Kali, and on the other of which was displayed the crab-like figure of Durga, faced each other” (77). Bankim later on goes for a huge course correction, to such an extent that his earlier hostility to Hinduism is today almost unknown outside serious Bankim scholars. When we are compelled to view ourselves through a prism borrowed from the west, it deflects our culture, it displaces our *dharma*, as it delays our nation-consciousness. But not subscribing to that discourse of western Enlightenment sometimes implies a more unfortunate regression into a forged pre-modern vision, neurotically and triumphantly obsessed with the golden Hindu past, complacently unaware of many

developments of modern history. So a denial of the western epistemology can be equally troublesome, if not more problematic. There can be a golden mean, and that can be called a synthesis, and it was precisely what Ishwarchandra himself (and still later Bankim) attempted, but this also inevitably results in a distortion, where our culture and identity get deflected and can never be identical with its pre-invasion form, as the prisms of western colonial hegemony end up besmirching our perspectives. Then we can only revisit our past as confused onlookers.

The only available image of Ishwar Gupta on the internet

Our argument is that in Ishwar Gupta's oeuvre we find an emerging Bengali nation-consciousness, where nineteenth century Kolkata is foregrounded as the space-time dimensions of that discourse. This discourse is, however, continually shredded, mutilated, violently rearranged and recast by colonial domination. Just like a black hole (or any massive object in the cosmos, for that matter) causes the space and time that it comes in contact with to curve, in a similar way, colonial subjugation has caused a curvature in Bengali identity, culture and history, and all attempts to re-assert them end up involving further distortions owing to the gravitational pull of the massive bulk of colonial infrastructure that continually affects the dimensions of our existence to this day. Bankim once famously told Ramkrishna that he became bent (Bankim in Sanskrit means bent, curved, crooked; that which is not straight) because of the kicks of the British boots (Bhattacharya 341). It was not a mere joke; there is a prophetic truth hidden in Bankim's utterance, we shall suggest.

The main proposition of this article is that at the core of the resistance movement against colonial oppression we can detect a deflection, a deferral of Bengali identity in order to accommodate the tremendous pressure of colonial domination. This statement is not a Derridean interpolation in the Bengali nationalist discourse; this is not a deconstructionist article in any particular way, and we have simply taken up the dictionary meaning of deferral. We are not particularly concerned with any Derridean *differance* here in this article. All we suggest here is that nation-consciousness is deferred in its very act of inception because of colonial pressure. Let us take an example. Dwijendranath Thakur reminisced about a national fair organised by Nabagopal Mitra (who was more popularly known as National Nabagopal, because he popularised the use of the word national in his various activities) where Dwijendranath to his horror discovered that a gigantic *deshi* painting (most likely a *potchitro*) depicted Indians with folded hands supplicating before Britannia (Bipin Gupta 274). For Nabagopal, this image was supposed to convey national art. Clearly that so called national fervour was not anti-colonial at all; it was submissive; very often it imitated the patriotism of the British, modelled itself on western-style nationalism, and was full of an Anglophile reverence for imperialism. National Nabagopal himself was a regular visitor to the corridors of colonial power and took pride in being close to British (Bipin Gupta 274-275). So there goes the inception of our nationalism proper.

The cover of this Sahitya Academy book in Hindi depicts the face of Ishwar Gupta quite differently

We have spoken of the hermeneutic damage caused by colonial domination (that continues to perpetrate itself in our country in spite of political independence, one may suggest). Let us take an example of what I would call interpretive violence, which happens when a western paradigm is imposed on Bengali culture. A recent critical appraisal of Ishwar Gupta done by Rosinka Chaudhuri titled “Poet of the Present” is a case in point. The main proposition of Rosinka Chaudhuri can be summed up in this statement from her article: “Ishwar Gupta's oeuvre is like the gossip in Hutom's Calcutta, which is constituted, as Ranajit Guha describes it, of an 'immediacy of presence' that 'as a phenomenon', lives only for the day, literally as ephemerous or *adyatana*, in a state of utter transience” (108).

In the course of our article we shall see that Ishwar Gupta's poetry is deeply concerned with the past and future of his country and countrymen. In an overzealous attempt to impose the ahistoricist, amnesiac and comprador cult of the *present* (a comprador always lives in the present, and celebrates the transient, as a comprador shares an Oedipal relation with his past and future; a comprador kills his past and screws his future, if we are allowed a moment of levity here), the significance of Gupta's activity as a compiler of old Bengali poetry of *Kobigān* is completely missed by this critic, who although is nominally aware of Ishwar Gupta's role as collector and editor of Bengali *Kobigān*, as the notes and bibliography at the end of her article attest. We shall also see that emboldened by this subaltern espousal (this article appears in an anthology edited by Partha Chatterjee *et al*), Chaudhuri enthusiastically goes on to compare Gupta with Baudelaire. In due course we shall show why there can be no comparison between Baudelaire and Ishwar Gupta. As an aside, this is indeed unfortunate that the subaltern group never questioned their own status as comprador intelligentsia. It might have made them realise their own position of utterance. But let us return to the matter at hand.

Let us remember that the birth of Kolkata is smeared in the filth of comprador politics, as this region was allotted by the Mughal commander Man Singh to Lokkhikanto (whose descendants, the Saborno Roy Choudhuris later sold Kolkata along with Gobindopur and Sutanuti to the East India Company) as a reward for their betrayal to Pratapaditya. Pramathanath Mallick points out that Kolkata in this sense was born with the zeitgeist (Kāla Dharma) of a fallen age (Kaliyuga), which means it was born in shackles of slavery, and it was somehow destined to continue in chains (16-17).

More importantly, colonial domination ensured (it still does) that we suffered from an anxiety of approval, where we needed to conform to western standards. As a result, Bengali culture was about to

be brutally split into the high and the low, as per the western norm prevalent in the nineteenth century. The elitist, bhadrakolok disdain for our own indigenous culture remained obvious in the attitude of the Kolkata intelligentsia as the nineteenth century gave way to the twentieth. We shall examine this following remark by Tagore in this connection: “In Greece the plays of Sophocles and Aeschylus were written and enacted not just for the VIPs. The common people there were fortunate not to have submitted to some Grecian Dashu Ray;” Tagore thus castigates the very idea of *Kobigān* in the sarcastic epithet “Grisiyo Dashu Ray.” He is referring to the legendary composer-singer of *Kobigān* and *Pānchāli*, Dashorothi Ray here, in a denigrating way in his letter to Dilipkumar Roy, compiled in the latter's *Collected Works* (624). Dashu Ray, we may note here, was a major influence on Ishwar Gupta as he learnt the secrets of the trade of poetry from the practitioners of *Kobigān* and half-*Ākhrāi* in his adolescence, as the foreword to Gupta's *Collected Works* points out (1: স্নাত্ত). Further, Professor Asitkumar Bandyopadhyay's foreword in Bipin Gupta's *Puraton Proshongo* mentions the pre-Bankim era as the age of Guptokobi (this was how Ishwar Gupta was popularly known) and Dashorothi Ray (পাঁচ), implying that the age saw a Dyarchy, where both Ishwarchandra Gupta and Dashorothi Ray ruled. Now, Tagore not only denigrates Dashu Ray; here he seems to have a haughty (and historically incorrect) view of the evolution of popular performative art forms across the world. It is sufficient to say here that Tagore displays a characteristic Brahmo and Victorian disdain for Bengali indigenous art forms of *Pānchāli* and *Kobigān* (which are rustic, uncouth and indecent for colonial standards) that spoke of our day to day experience with a sturdy materialism, without taking any recourse to, say, the vague mysticism of a Lalan Fakir or sophisticated romanticism of a Tagore. *Kobigān* often tends to challenge the soft lyricism of Tagorean Bengali poetry. It indulges into raw human aesthetics without the invention of romantic or spiritual love. It too had its religious and devotional lyrics, but most of the times, it spoke in a straightforward and materialist manner, without any mystification. It was therefore popular among the masses, who loved its substantial entertainments.

Popularity was again a matter to be suspicious of, and one reason why Dashu Ray was low was that he was popular, an artist of the masses. Popular culture, for a very long time, was low culture (prior to the upheaval staged by Raymond Williams called cultural studies, a western phenomenon that now encourages numerous Indian critics like Chaudhuri to refocus on popular culture *a la* the western framework that for quite some time now has been in vogue). However, our comprador intelligentsia can scarcely move out of their hegemonic, holier-than-thou, liberal-humanist piety even when they are

supposedly working on low, popular culture, and therefore Ishwar Gupta is lambasted by Chaudhuri in these terms: “It is the language he uses against the Muslims that is most offensive... Such sentiments, expressed with an appalling coarseness of language, in the context of Muslims, are repeatedly present in poems” (97). This prescriptive approach of political correctness and high-minded secularism of a necessarily elite, bhadralok perspective, when mixed with a West-inspired, newly found, neophytic zeal for the popular culture, together give birth to a mulish hybridity. There is mutilation and there is critical malformation for us. It does not occur to this critic that Gupta might simply have been reflecting the popular sentiment of his readers when he is speaking against Muslims, because such an idea would unsettle quite a number of haloed liberal humanist assumptions.

The continuum between the past and the present is therefore doubly threatening for colonialism. Not just the past offers a resistance to the dominant west-influenced distortions which have become commandments for those under the spell of liberal humanist amnesia, the past is in league with the present (however out of joint that present may be) as they secretly, subversively hatch a conspiracy together to bring about their own guerrilla readings against the grain of received standards. The politically incorrect art forms can live on in an underground manner. An obituary written in poetry by Srijato (published in a magazine on 15 November, 2012, shared on his facebook.com page) after Sunil Ganguly's death not just evokes Kolkata, it (unwittingly) evokes the tradition of the birds (*Pakhi*), where those young poets who were close to Sunil are compared to birds. This particular piece by Kolkata's popular poet-lyricist Srijato, it seems, is affected by a historical unconscious where the *Pokkhis* of nineteenth century Kolkata seem to form a continuum with a group of poets of twenty-first century.

The poetic obituary for Sunil written by Srijato which compares young Kolkata poets to bird/pakhi

Well, while talking of Kolkata, and *Kobigān* (as we shall presently explore in details Ishwar Gupta's collation of the lives and works of *Kobiyals*), one cannot escape the recent phenomenon of the Bengali movie named *Jatishshor* which is a narration of the life of Anthony Firingi, the Bengali *Kobiyal* per excellence who was not a Bengali by birth, but was a Bengali by choice. Here let us note that throughout this article we use the traditional word *Kobiwala* (as used by Ishwar Gupta himself in his pioneering studies of *Kobigān*) instead of *Kobiyal*. The word *Kobi* in the context of *Kobigān* meant a piece of song, and not what the word is conventionally taken to mean, which is poet. Bankim points out that in *Kobir Lorai*, it was the composition that was called *Kobi* (716), hence the origin of the term *Kobiwala*, which meant a stockist/seller/dealer of *Kobi*, denoting the person who composed and/or sang in *Kobir Lorai*. Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay affirms that Ishwar Gupta was *the pioneer* of collecting *Kobigān* and observes that all anthologies of the compositions of the *Kobiwalas* which have appeared since the days of Gupta are indebted wholly to Gupta and all have borrowed from his collection (1: 467). Sadly, Gupta is almost never acknowledged.

A still from the movie *Jatishshor*

The present researcher observed Kabir Suman's (the music director of the movie *Jatishshor*) castigation of Tagore in an interview aired on ABP Ananda on 16 April 2014, retecast on 17 April 2014, between 10 pm and 11pm. Further, in a facebook status update dated 17 April 2014 Kabir Suman attacked the 'landed-gentry' aspect of Tagore which arguably led the Nobel Laureate to denounce the marginal culture of *Kobiyal-Kobigān*. This is a confused application of Marxian notion of class war to the

economic situation of nineteenth century Bengal, because that class of landed gentry, far from showing a wholesale hostility to *Kobigān*, was very often its chief patron, as we shall see. Suman's is not a historically valid observation, but then liberal humanism does not care for history, and is solely driven by an amnesiac individual's grandstanding declarations. However, we cannot deny that rediscovering the tradition of *Kobigān* is one major contribution generated by the phenomenal response evoked by this award winning film, *Jatishshor*. Let us now have a look at Kabir Suman's statement:

“It was not Kabir Suman who got the award. It was Bengal's music. The great texts written by the wonderful Kabiyaals of Bengal, whose work and contributions have always been belittled by the Bengali gentry, their stupendous command over our language, its movement, its texture, its power, its SOUND, its abundance and over meter made me compose the melodies for the 13 songs. I wonder why not even Rabindranath Thakur tried to assess the Kabiyaals' contributions. WAS IT BECAUSE THE KABIYALS REPRESENTED THE COMMON PEOPLE AND NOT THE LANDED GENTRY? In my work I was influenced by Bengal's Kirtan, Ramprosad tunes, Bangla Paala tunes and movements, Bhairabi baul, different modes of Shyamasangeet, Hindustani raagas, Bangla "boiThoki gaan"... My own songs are a continuation of Bangla Adhunik Gaan which, again, has always used raagas, Bengali folk music, Kirtan and European music. Out of all these different elements the IDIOMS of Modern Bengali Songs were created. I thank Srijit Mukherjee and the producers once again for giving me this opportunity to expose at least some aspects of Bengal's Music to the world”. (facebook.com, 17 Apr 2014)

Now, Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay's anthology attests that *Kobigān* was immensely popular as the chief medium of popular entertainment in early nineteenth century Kolkata with the wealthy Bengalis as its patrons; a *Kobir Lorai* between two troupes from Jorashnako and Bagbajar is narrated in a report of 1829: the competition was held at the house of Gurucharan Mullick at Doyehata (1: 144). Bhabatosh Dutta informs us that Ishwar Gupta was the songmaker (*badhondar*) of the Bagbajar troupe in this competition (*Ishwarchandra Gupta Rochito Kobijiboni* | ১০).

Many other contemporary reports establish that the rich people were the patrons of *Kobigān* and used to organise these soirées at their residences. *Kobigān* was uprooted not because of the hostility of the landed gentry (in fact we see that the patronage of the landed gentry was its lifeline and was what allowed *Kobigān* to survive), but because of the Western influence among the bhadralok Bengalis. *Kobigān* caused that anxiety of approval, as the Victorian norms gravely expressed their disapproval of

this form. This genre of songs, associated with Bengal's pre-British past, came to mean regress, and it took superhuman efforts on the part of Ishwar Gupta, as we shall soon see in this article, to rescue *Kobigān* and the *Kobiwalas* from oblivion. Gupta was never acknowledged by anyone from the team of *Jatishshor* in the midst of this entire fanfare, which once more establishes how past becomes suppressed, censored and distorted in the triumphant march of colonial, liberal modernity. *Kobigān* as an indigenous art form came to be associated with an uncouth, uneducated, rustic, un-enlightened, non-Victorian, indecent milieu which had to be forgotten and annihilated if Bengalis needed to move forward in a colonially approved telos of modernity. When Bankim heaves a sigh, “খাঁটি বাঙালি কবি আর জন্মায় না - জন্মিবাব উপায় নাই - জন্মিয়া কাজ নাই” (Pure Bengali poets are no longer born – there's no way they can be born – there's no use in having them born) (706), we detect the trauma of an insufferable nostalgia felt by a generation mutilated and alienated by progress, looking back askance at an organic past that is now forever lost.

Chitpur, neighbouring Bagbajar. Painting by James Baillie Fraser, 1826

However, the one aspect of Tagore (that Kabir Suman completely misses out) that makes him hostile to *Kobigān* is that Tagore represents the enlightened western liberal universalism, and *Kobigān* stands for a 'regressive' Bengali parochial lowly art form. Farther, *Kobigān* as a collective art form (there were always teams and troupes and never singular, standalone poets in this genre) might have been injurious to Tagore's predominantly individualist sensibility. Tagore also displays a dismissive attitude to Ishwar Gupta himself when he speaks of Bankim's *awkward* apprenticeship of language under the tutelage of Ishwar Gupta, a suggestion which is incidentally challenged by noted Bankim scholar Amitrasudan Bhattacharya (11). Bhattacharya observes that Ishwar Gupta in his editorial comment following Bankim's published piece in *Shongbād Probhākor* pointed out that the writer should not burden his poetry with an excessive dependence on lexicon; Bhattacharya further believes that Ishwar Gupta's regime was not responsible for whatever weakness existed in Bankim's first published prose, as “Ishwar Gupta himself in his prose was ahead of his time” (13).

Let us return to *Kobigān*. Rediscovery of *Kobigān* has somehow been linked to the Bengali liberal humanist fanfare over baul, but our progressive secular-liberal universal humanists (in a word, *bishshomanob* as we call in Bengali) rarely note that there are strong differences between these two genres. Baul was an inverted way to celebrate western liberalism, an indigenous art form moulded and reshaped and adequately sanitised to suit an individualist sensibility. *Kobigān*, in Suman's version however, tries to keep up with largely the same liberal-imperial motif of the market of *mohamilon* or the Ananda Bazar Patrika Abbey, where Indic Bengalis are required to surrender each one of their unique civilisational heritages in favour of some bogus hybridity (bogus, because the moment we stop taking it at face value, it will reveal itself as a façade behind which the systematic aggression of West, Islam and other colonising forces against the indigenous culture of Bengal is hidden). The trajectory of *Kobigān* as an art form remains recalcitrant and obtuse vis-a-vis all hegemonic attempts of standardisation, and does not yield to appropriation as easily as the mystification of *baul* yielded to western hegemony. This new interest in the deeply parochial genre of *Kobigān* (the spirit of which is captured in the message of Ishwar Gupta: embrace the native dog, forsaking foreign god)¹ might later embarrass those Western liberals among us who are trying to idealise the figure of the *Kobiwala* on the model of the *approved* figure of *baul*, if they get to know more about the indispensable association of the history of *Kobigān* with Ishwar Gupta.

It has been customary to underestimate Ishwar Gupta, the man who ruled Bengali literature in the pre-Bankim, pre-Madhusudan era. He is our major figure who curiously remains more obscure than a host of minor figures. While Romesh Chunder Dutt in his *The Literature of Bengal* observes Ishwar Gupta's strategic position within a society in transition, and his role as a link between the poetry of the past and the present, he does not assign any significant place to Ishwar Gupta as a poet: "As a poet Ishwar Gupta does not rank very high,, as a satirist he stands first among the writers of Bengal" (151). Clearly the overt post-romantic milieu interferes with a proper evaluation of Ishwar Gupta, because he was the poet of "jaha aache" (that what is present), as Bankim put it so succinctly (717), yet mistakenly, as we shall see. As the mood of the west-inspired romantic zeitgeist favoured that which was not there, that which could only be accessed through a flight of imagination, creative writing sufficiently displaced the everyday to point where it resembled the exotic, warded off the vulgar to the point where poetry became venerable. This Romantic sensibility is also at work in Bankim, who says that there's no use in having a pure Bengali poet any more. A poet like Ishwar Gupta who can only write about those things which are here and now becomes therefore a liability. Since Bankim said this, this became an ultimate shortcut in the criticism of Ishwar Gupta. The best way to form an opinion about Gupta without reading him, it seems, is to read this particular phrase of Bankim.

So it is very convenient to forget that Ishwar Gupta is the first chronicler of the lives and works

of Bengali poets and songmakers of pre-colonial and early colonial past. It is equally expedient to ignore that Gupta was deeply concerned about the future of Bengali literature, too. This ignoring attitude is evident in Rosinka Chaudhuri's article. We should observe in all fairness that as Kolkata was preparing to stage its literary and cultural renaissance, it was Gupta who did the work of masonry for that stage. In March 1853, Ishwar Gupta in his *Shongbād Probhākor* organised a “collegiate battle of poetry” (*Kalejiyo Kobitajuddho*), where Bankim (then a student of Hooghly College), Dinabandhu Mitra (then a student of Presidency College) and Dwarakanath Adhikary (then a student of Krishnanagar College) participated in what was a periodical's version of *Kobir Lorai* (literally, battle of poets, it meant the competition of *Kobiwalas* in front of an open audience) (Bhattacharya 16).

Dinabandhu Mitra

Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay

Dwarakanath was awarded the first prize, and his early death ensured that he remained the only unknown figure among these three. The other two entered the status of immortality in Bengali literature. Dwarakanath died very young, and Bankim later reminisced about Dwarakanath in these terms: “His writing method was somewhat simple and transparent like Ishwar Gupta – he used to express native feeling in native words. He died in tender age. If he lived, perhaps he would have become an excellent poet” (Bhattacharya 17). Bankim's poetry was first published in Gupta's *Shongbād Probhākor* on 25 February 1852 (Bhattacharya 24). Bhattacharya quotes Bankim in this regard:

Bengali literature was then in a bad shape. *Probhakor* then was the most superior newspaper. Ishwar Gupta used to rule single-handedly over Bengali literature. Young men having been impressed with his poetry were eager to get introduced to him. Ishwar Gupta (too) was specially inclined to encourage young writers. *Hindu Patriot* rightly observed that many among the modern writers are disciples of Ishwar Gupta. ... just as the excellent writers like Dinabandhu Mitra, this small writer is also indebted to Ishwar Gupta. (25)

Quite interestingly, Ishwar Gupta in his editorial advice reviewing Bankim's poetry asked the latter to avoid the “dear words of the old poets” like “এবে, কনয়ে, ছেঁনু, গেঁনু ” (Bhattacharya 25-26), which not only establishes Gupta's progressiveness as an editor-advisor in discouraging archaic forms of words, but also points towards an underlying trend in Bengali poetry since then: its attempt to stay as close to the lived speech as possible. Gupta initiated this trend in Bengali literature, taking his cue from *Kobigān* which as a tradition definitely contravenes against all arcane literary methods and mystifications of archaicism. Ishwar Gupta champions that indigenous tradition of simple, colloquial, lively speech.

The formation of nation-consciousness is initiated by a collage of different materials taken together, and which can be the better place for such a miscellany than the concatenation offered by a daily newspaper? Gupta was the editor of what was to become the first Bengali daily, *Shongbād Probhākor*, where he attempted a synthesis of different threads of Bengalis experience in order to forge a common network. As an editor of a daily, he certainly was not exclusively confined to matters of literary significance, and he participated in different social and cultural activities. An 1837 newspaper report stands testimony to Gupta's attachment to the Bengali nationalist cause as he participated in a meeting of *Bongobhasha Prokashika Shomaj* that resolved to protest against the government's new policy of extracting revenue out of lands which used to be untaxed earlier (Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay 2: 404-405). Clearly this refers to the places of worship, which traditionally have been untaxed.

Gupta tried to achieve a consolidation of Bengali identity as the readership of his newspaper continued to grow: this could be thought of a centripetal movement that proposed to initiate a space and time coordination of the Bengali people which would ultimately bring forth a consolidation of nation-consciousness, and attempt a network formation in geographical, cultural and historical terms. Nation formation in modern period through the printing press is not a novel concept, it was suggested by Benedict Anderson in *Imagined Communities* (this book, by the way, is one of the most misunderstood works on nationalism; Anderson is generally sympathetic to nationalism, while anti-nationalism critics have made his concept to appear to suggest a fictitious nature of nationalism; Anderson suggests that a nation is an imagined community, not an immediate community like, say, the one constituted by members of a committee, or neighbours in a housing estate where everyone personally knows other members of one's community; the international workers' movement is also an imagined movement, or a huge rally of

a million people is also an imagined procession, because someone present there does not know everybody else).

There is a poetics of *coordiNation* in Ishwar Gupta, as we shall see. A portmanteau of coordination and nation, this term I want to coin in order to explain the work of Ishwar Gupta. Having a meaning that it self-evidently conveys, this word captures the spirit of Gupta's project which wanted to achieve a consolidation of the Bengali people, an alignment of the past with the present, bringing together different interest groups and different strata of society; it was this project that was historically undertaken in *Shongbād Probhākor*. In his project of *coordiNation*, Gupta is critical of imperialism but is never rebellious against it, therefore his *coordiNation* simultaneously posits and deflects Bengali nation-consciousness. Further, it frequently undercuts various forms of the wasteful, diffusive Romantic universalism (Bhadralok-ish, Brahmo, educated, Tagorean) which is already becoming prominent in nineteenth century Kolkata and would later come to characterise and dominate Bengali society and culture. Gupta's *coordiNation* is decidedly urban without being cosmopolitan, as opposed to the liberal-humanist emphasis of a bhadralok ethos that wants to defer the lowliness of the real in favour of the exotic imaginary of the ideal, wants to displace history by getting confined to an amnesiac present, wants to deflect the indigenous by centring the universal, and ultimately wants to defer the community by upholding the individual. *CoordiNation* is notably blasé too, as it is more concerned with an arrangement of available elements of reality than with any flights of fancy. *CoordiNation* is also more nuanced and accommodative in its approach to the past, and is not prescriptive like the elite, bhadralok outlook. Gupta's *coordiNation* becomes a register of the cityscape of the nineteenth century Kolkata, delineating the dialectics of nation-consciousness that was in making. Finally, Gupta's project of *coordiNation* subverts colonialism at the strategic faultlines.

Liberal humanist universalism remains a force of collaboration, and plays its part by rallying its bulk behind the colonial power, further facilitating the deflection and deferral of the task of weaving together different aspects and dimensions of Bengaliness. Gupta himself belonged to the urban folk tradition of *Kobigān* and half-*Ākhrāi*, but we shall see that contrary to popular perceptions, he mastered the colonial standards equally well. He participated in various literary and philosophical societies, and moved in erudite, western-educated company, yet he was an “uneducated” fellow, bereft of western-style school and college education. He was associated with the Brahmos and we would see that Bankim considered that Gupta officially converted himself to Brahmoism. Gupta's God was characteristically

Brahmo, as we can see in his writing (1: 280ff). Though *Probhakor* was supportive of traditional Hinduism at the time of its inception, during the course of its initial year of publication it slowly gravitated to Brahmoism; another contemporary periodical made this observation (Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay 2: 185). Gupta's treatise on the nature of God, also exploring the relation of human beings with the divine, written in the format of a question-answer session between a father and his son, which also included long devotional poems, came to constitute the text *Probodh Probhakor* that had a distinctly paternalist notion of God (1: 291ff). But interestingly, as commentator Tripurashankar Senshasutri points out in the introduction to the second volume of Gupta's *Collected Works*, the scheme of theology Gupta offers here is also highly influenced by Sankhya philosophy (2: পনেরো). There is truth in this observation, though Gupta's treatise is theist to the core (unlike Sankhya). Sankhya has remained the dominant philosophical system in Bengal, informing both Shaktoism and Boishnobism, and this was one of the core arguments in my article in the previous issue of JBS (Vol. 3 No. 1). Gupta's synthesis of Brahmo philosophy and Sankhya philosophy brings together diverse elements from different spheres of nineteenth century Kolkata, joining polytheistic idolatry with monistic worship.

Lalbajar, Kolkata. James Baillie Fraser, 1826

However, Gupta's overt submission to an idea of a singular male God subscribing to the Brahma paradigm (which in turn not just derived its influence from Upanishada but also from the Semitic, Judeo-Christian-Islamic conceptions of God) sometimes made his position askew to Shakti Worship, the most important indigenous religious tradition of Bengal, Bengal's *Boishnobism* remaining a distant second in terms of influence. Interestingly, in Gupta's play *Bodhendu Bikash* Goddess Saraswati is seen to advise a devotee to dedicate himself to the worship of the idol forms of Shri Hari or Durga if he is unable to contemplate on the worship of the indifferent, formless *ParamaBrahma* (*Collected Works* 2: 349). This might as well be a Kolkata bhadralok's red-faced compromise with the superstitious systems of *Shakto* and *Boishnob* idolatry reeking heavily of maternal worship (be it Kali or Radha) which his paternalist bosses from Islamic or Christian or liberal-rational or communist orders have alike despised down the ages. But this invests Gupta precisely with that bhadralok respectability which is otherwise arguably lacking in some of his poems. It is interesting to note that his *Collected Works* exclude some of his so called obscene poems, but include those works which are respectable by bhadralok standards, even if they are boring, and carry little or no literary substance. *Bodhendu Bikash* is one such play which is disastrous as a work of literature but is measured high in terms of elitism, respectability and chaste language (it is an adaptation of a Sanskrit play named *Prabodha Chandrodaya*).

Himself without an English education, Gupta remains remarkably receptive towards the colonial system of studies, and speaks of the students of the three colleges of Kolkata, Krishnanagar and Hooghly as the exemplary ones, who are fit for emulation for the young Bengalis elsewhere (1: 289). Clearly this is an indirect praise for Dinabandhu, Dwarkanath and Bankim. More importantly, this establishes Gupta's alignment with colonial education, though he was not himself a product of it. Though Gupta continued to speak of God in distinctly Brahma terms, yet he remained an idolatrous Hindu to the core, occasionally revelling in the *Shakto* worship of Durga and Kali. Gupta was a pure Bengali poet, Bankim famously states, forgetting that Ishwar Gupta was also the first major Bengali writer to have used English words in Bengali poems. These are not insurmountable contradictions: the ideal individual subject of liberal-humanist thought may be an integer, but in real social practice, a human subject is always an assemblage of diverse cultural and historical currents, which are often cross-currents. Ishwar Gupta is an exemplary proponent of this assemblage, this collage of the indigenous and the foreign. The making of the modern Bengali identity is full of contradictions which nineteenth century Kolkata embodies. Some of the indigenous components of this collage later get suppressed, and many of the west-inspired

elements get highlighted, as the colonisation of the Bengali people attain greater proportions, further deferring the making of nation-consciousness.

One aspect of this colonisation is a growing elitism, another is a disregard for the local in favor of a grandiose vision of *the* Global. Naturally, Ishwar Gupta's famous poetic proclamation to embrace a country dog forsaking the foreign God became an anathema for the later ages steadily bred on a diet of universal humanism or *bishshomanobota*. A routine condemnation of Gupta's narrowness has therefore become mandatory on the part of all commentators, as the foreword to his collected works does the same (1: নম্ব). However, such liberal critics of Gupta's narrowness rarely notice that this affection otherwise offered to the dog of native country is not (in a rather discriminatory manner) offered to the native crow! Gupta's hostility towards the leaders of 1857 great war of independence is recorded in one of his poems, where Rani Jhansi is compared to a crow with chopped lips (implying that she emits harsh sounds in a brazen manner) (qtd. in 1: পনেরো). The comprador features of Bengali intelligentsia prevailed here. In any case the rebels against the Raj were perhaps more foreign to the Bengali babus than the British rulers themselves. The nascent nation-consciousness, mortgaged to British imperialism, remains bent and deflected since inception.

Nineteenth century Kolkata is exposed in all its rawness in Gupta, who is frequently criticised by later generations for the fault of obscenity and also for lack of sophistication; the introduction to his collected works does that, for instance (2: উনিশ). It is true that there is no craft of concealment in his writings, and that his wiring is bare. His superstructure readily betrays its foundation, and his artistic devices remain uncovered, as if in a Brechtian theatre. What might strike an honest critic (who does not dismiss Gupta in an offhanded manner as a mere cog in the nineteenth century Calcutta wheel evoking little more than archaeological curiosity) as a plethora of contradictions is actually the organic framework of a writer's works as this writer in question is revealed to be a representative of the nationalist awakening of Bengal with all its promises and problems. Sadly, that has not been the case, and Gupta has been a victim of negligence, simplifications and sweeping generalisations. That Ishwar Gupta is a writer of triviality, temporality, tendentiousness and terrible alliterations has become a critical commonplace. He is considered to have become quickly outdated, as critics and commentators since Bankim routinely point out. Gupta is charged with obscenity by an age that wants to purge the last vestiges of any non-bhadralok sensibilities. His classicist, realist, satirist sensibility soon became out of joint in an age dominated by post-Romantic slumber of Victorian pieties, and so the lofty, high-minded, noble-intentioned, elite poets

like Nabinchandra, Madhusudan and Hemchandra soon replaced him with their turgid idealism which thoroughly smacked of Romantic sloppiness, Victorian prudery, approved colonial standards of literature and high culture, while Bengali society began its long, noble trek towards Tagore. Since then no one ever tried to rescue Ishwar Gupta from the infamy which is customarily heaped on him. Gupta as the defender of the indigenous has been largely neglected by subsequent generations who remained embarrassed not just with Gupta's lack of western-style education, but also with Gupta's brazen espousal of pre-modern, pre-British styles of Bengali poetry, thus continually postponing a proper evaluation of Ishwar Gupta. Let us examine here what Bankim said about Ishwar Gupta (rather harshly and unsympathetically, but he is being typical of this new generation of western educated intelligentsia):

“He was a very remarkable man. He was ignorant and uneducated. He knew no language but his own, and was singularly narrow and unenlightened in his views; yet for more than twenty years he was the most popular author among the Bengalis. As a writer of light satiric verse, he occupied the first place, and he owed his success both as a poet and as an editor to this special gift. But there his merits ended. Of the higher qualities to a poet he possessed none, and his work was extremely rude and uncultivated. His writings were generally disfigured by the grossest obscenity. His popularity was chiefly owing to his perpetual alliteration and play upon words. We have purposely noticed him here in order to give the reader an idea of the literary capacity and taste of the age in his a poetaster like Iswar Chandra Gupta obtained the highest rank in public estimation. And we cannot even say that her did not deserve to be placed in the highest rank among his Bengali contemporaries, for he was man of some literary talent, while none of the others possessed any. How much we may lament the poverty of Bengali literature, the last fifteen years have been a period of great progress and hope; within that time at least a dozen writers have arisen, everyone of whom is immensely superior in whatever is valuable as a writer, to this – the most popular of their predecessors.

Strange as it may appear, this obscure end (sic) often immoral writer was one of the precursors of the modern Brahmists. The charge of obscenity and immorality mainly applies to his poetry. His prose is generally free from both vices, and often advocates the cause of religion and morality.” (qtd. in Bhattacharya 204-205)

What we observe in Bankim's statement is a censuring: Gupta is appreciated only so far as his writing conforms to the norms and standards approved by nineteenth century colonial sensibility. Even today, as we have seen, Gupta continues to be misinterpreted and abused by the standard-bearers of the western liberal-humanist order.

But it is worse when Gupta comes to be colonised and appropriated, because we tend to think that a writer like him is immune from liberal appropriation. A proud declaration adorns the foreword of the posthumous edition of *Shottonarayoner Brotokotha* (first published in the Bengali Year 1319, reproduced in the second volume of Gupta's *Collected Works*): “Madhusudan is Bengal's – Milton. Hemchandra – Pindar. Nabinchandra – Byron. Rabindranath, Shelley; ... But what is Ishwar Gupta to Bengal? Ishwar Gupta is Bengal's Ishwar Gupta” (144). There used to be this assurance among Bengali nationalists that Ishwar Gupta was nonpareil, that at least he could not be tagged with a Western identity like other writers. Bankim himself gave such an impression in his essay on Gupta. Well, that is no longer the case. That assurance suffers a terminal onslaught when Ishwar Gupta is compared to Baudelaire by Rosinka Chaudhuri in her article, albeit completely disregarding the fact that Ishwar Gupta had a traumatic colonial experience to deal with, unlike Baudelaire. France was already a nation per excellence, Bengalis were yet to forge their identity. Ishwar Gupta did not enjoy the luxury to become a rootless individual deliberating on the angst of urban experience, freefloating like the flaneur from Baudelaire's works, as Chaudhuri suggests (104). Chaudhuri proceeds to observe in Gupta a (Baudelaire-like) motion of popular, mass poetry in the backdrop of the giant city of Kolkata:

“Keeping in mind the essentially urban character of Iswar Gupta's poetry, it should be possible to see, in Benjamin's foregrounding in Baudelaire of the metropolitan masses that inhabit 'giant cities', the public as it was taking shape in mid-nineteenth century Calcutta. The verse of Iswar Gupta, so different in form from his French contemporary, was similarly inhabited by the pressure of a public made up of 'the people in the street' ... For Iswar Gupta, these are the readers of a poetry which, both in its physical incarnation and its content, was essentially poetry that was designed to be sold in the streets.” (Chaudhuri 92)

In support of this view, Chaudhuri quotes from Shibnath Shastri: “When the *Prabhākar* was published, newspaper-sellers would stand at the cross-roads and read aloud from the poetry in it and in no time at all a huge number of papers would be sold” (92-93). However, as the present researcher investigated the life and works of Gupta, it became evident that Gupta did not herald a poetry movement for the people

on the urban streets in a Baudelairean fashion, in the vein of some Marxist telos that depicts the progress of bourgeoisie. Gupta was necessarily addressing the educated middle and upper class Bengalis through his newspaper. At the most, Shastri can be deduced to be claiming that Gupta wrote for the people on the cross roads, and not really for the people on the street in the manner of some Parisian poet. Literacy level and colonial circumstances of Kolkata would scorn at Chaudhuri's far-fetched attempt to compare between Baudelaire's Paris and Gupta's Kolkata. However, Chaudhuri is right to point out some of the pioneering works done by Gupta in *Shongbād Probhākor*:

“The *Sambād Prabhākar* was perhaps the first Indian regional language newspaper to carry a literary supplement – from the Bengali New Year of 1853 it published a monthly supplement that provided a much more substantial space than the daily newspaper for the publication of a variety of occasional verse, as well as an eclectic range of prose and imaginative writing, providing Iswar Gupta with more space in which to indulge his creative output than was available in the news-oriented daily newspaper.” (Chaudhuri 93-94)

Use of the term “regional language” is highly objectionable, but there is little doubt that being the first vernacular daily newspaper in the subcontinent, it was indeed the first to carry a literary supplement. The monthly literary supplement of *Shongbād Probhākor* that Ishwar Gupta started is very highly praised by Krishnakamal Bhattacharya, who also mentions Gupta's repute as an acclaimed *badhondar* or composer of *kobigān* in the same vein (Bipin Gupta 55).

Interestingly, though Gupta could not sing himself, as he had a husky voice, but songs composed by him used to be sung in all the villages of Bengal (সেকালে তাঁহার গান বাঙ্গলার পল্লীতে পল্লীতে গীত হইত) (Bipin Gupta 55). Further, Krishnakamal reminisces that the original, pre-British method of writing Bengali, that was unspoilt by westernisation and at the same time was not burdened with undue Sanskritisation could be found in Bharatchandra, Dashorothi Ray and Ishwarchandra Gupta (Bipin Gupta 56). Ishwar Gupta commanded a folk popularity that was unparalleled, and he held a tremendous appeal for the educated upper and middle classes too. Furthering the consolidation of his people through the vehicle of literature was crucial to Gupta's project of coordination: “From 1851 onward, Iswar Gupta began to organize a literary festival in Calcutta on the day of the Bengali New Year on the 15th of April at his printing press” (Chaudhuri 94). This may be an example of Gupta's ingenuity to invent a new tradition (another process that is central to nationalism). The customary ritual of *Halkhata* of the New Year (beginning of fresh book-keeping at the business establishments) was creatively transformed into

a celebration of Bengali poetry. Renowned poet Nabinchandra Sen's account of the reception of Ishwar Gupta's poetic, journalistic and other works during his childhood and youth in Chittagong in the 1850s is quite significant: “In those days, Bengal's Saraswati Devi's pale and poor image was to be found installed at the *baṭṭalā*. There, whatever was birthed by the Mother on the poorest paper in illegible print – I read it all. Gradually, Iswarchandra Gupta and the god-like (*deb-pratim*) Iswarchandra Vidyasagar began to dawn upon the sky of Bengali literature” (qtd. in Chaudhuri 94). Encouraged by Nabinchandra's juxtaposition of Saraswati and *bot-tola*, Chaudhuri goes on to trace a fusion of the high and the low in Gupta: “The self-division of Bengali modernity, at odds between the *baṭṭalā* and Saraswati Devī, found a fusion of form and figure in the personality of Iswar Gupta in mid-nineteenth century Bengal” (95).

Nabin Chandra Sen

A Nineteenth Century Bot-tola imprint of Goddess Saraswati

However, the present researcher would maintain that it is an error to think of Ishwar Gupta in terms of fusion (of the high and the low), because he championed a culture that existed prior to that fissure (which separated the Bengali elites from the Bengali masses) brought about by colonialism. To call that culture a fusion is to seriously misinterpret it, because that culture still held its internal coherence, no matter how great the external disturbance was. Gupta himself emphasises a certain ability of the *Kobiwalas* to appeal to the elites and the masses alike, and recounts one anecdote where Nitai Boiragi is shown to have seamlessly pleased the elites and masses alike by singing songs from his impressive repertoire which had fast, rhythmic songs for the masses as well as slow, romantic songs for the elites (1:167).

Some may suggest that this eventual segregation owed to an increased Sanskritisation, but as Bankim points out, Hindu sages never held any prejudice against the use of so-called low languages, and even indulged in it while making a point or while venting their anger in high debates and scholarly dissensions (719). Rosinka Chaudhuri comments that Ishwar Gupta was censured by Bankim for obscenity (98); the fact of the matter is that Bankim in his essay defended Gupta on this point, since Bankim realised that the nuances of our tradition should not be collapsed and deflated in order to conform to western norms. But otherwise it is true that Bankim too was helpless in front of this tide of westernisation. An anxiety to secure respect from foreign rulers forced nineteenth century Bengalis to adhere to Victorian standards, freaking at the obscenity of their indigenous tradition. A paper titled “Bengali Poetry” that was written and read by Horochondro Dutta, an Anglophile, at the Bethune Society on 8 April 1852 very heavily criticised its subject matter, i.e. Bengali poetry for being vulgar and profligate, as Bhabatosh Dutta in his editorial commentary to *Ishwarchandra Gupta Rochito Kobijiboni* points out (1).

Utpal Dutt in his *Girish Manosh* repeatedly emphasises the role of Ishwar Gupta in fostering a native, folk sensibility that also influenced the theatre of Girish Ghosh. Dutt says that Girish actually worshipped Ishwar Gupta (31), and observes that not only Girish was an admirer (*gunomugdho*) of Ishwar Gupta, Girish himself was a practitioner of the performative form of half-*Ākhrāi*, a form much favoured by Gupta himself (3). While Tagore was summarily dismissive of *Kobigān*, and in a rather elitist manner looked down upon it as vulgar and deviant, not conforming to proper aesthetics (*jothartha shahittorosh*), Vidyasagar once quite famously made a statement in favour of the *Kobiwalas*, when he said that in order to keep the Bengali society alive, the advent of *Kobiwalas* like Bhola Moyra is essential (qtd. in Utpal Dutt 35).

Noted actor Asit Baran as Bhola Moyra; a still from Uttam Kumar-starrer Anthony Firingi (1967)

Vidyasagar's espousal of *Kobigān*, who was one of the greatest Sanskrit scholars who ever lived in India, representing the best of the Brahminical scholarly tradition of Bengal, perhaps is a case in point: the fissure that is brought about in the wake of colonialism has not yet been able to segregate the high from the low, the respectable from the vulgar, the decent from the obscene, the elite from the masses in the nineteenth century Kolkata that Ishwar Gupta belongs to. Ishwar Gupta is a representative of the same sensibility which Vidyasagar seems to have shared and which by the time of Tagore came under severe assault. However, it would be wrong to assert an unproblematic stance of Vidyasagar in favour of Bengali nation-consciousness. On one hand, he stood for Sanskrit College, an institution where he studied and later became the Principal. That institution was started by Orientalists (those western scholars who had a paternalistic, patronising attitude to Indian culture), but later came under assault from the Anglicists (who wanted the imperial administration to aggressively promote English language and culture at the cost of Sanskrit and vernacular). Macaulay, the arch-Anglicist wanted to abolish Sanskrit College itself (Bipin Gupta 118), and then a Sanskrit shloka was written by Joygopal Torkalonkar (Vidyasagar's teacher) addressed to the chief patron of this college, Horace Heyman Wilson, that translates like this: his Sanskrit Pathshala is like a lake, and the pundits who have been placed by you here are like swans, but a few cruel hunters having come near this lake are now about to kill them. If you protect the swans from these hunters, your deed will be immortal (Bipin Gupta 118-119). Clearly, Vidyasagar too must have suffered from that insecurity as a scholar of Sanskrit which Sanskrit as a subject suffered under increasing momentum of cultural colonialism.

Vidyasagar confided in Krishnakamal Bhattacharya, his close disciple, towards the end of his life: “Whatever else I do or not to the kids, will certainly never again teach them English. Such a path to become empty (অসার) and over-smart (ডেঁপো)!” (Bipin Gupta 117). But on the other hand, the same Vidyasagar ironically initiated a number of pro-English reforms in Sanskrit College when he became the Principal; he made English compulsory in the higher classes, he stopped Sanskrit as a medium of learning Mathematics as traditional Sanskrit texts for learning mathematics were also withdrawn, and in their stead English textbooks were introduced (Bipin Gupta 19). We know from other sources that Vidyasagar stopped the teaching learning of a number of Indian philosophical traditions, including that of Sankhya and Vedanta, on the ground that they were “false” systems of thought (Sumit Sarkar vainly defends Vidyasagar on this ground in his essay 119-120). Macaulay already stopped the teaching-learning of Ayurveda in Sanskrit college by a government order dated 28 January 1835. In fact, there was a

coordinated attempt to dissociate Sanskrit from science.

Further, Marshman's History of Bengal, which was a deeply imperial text denigrating the Bengali people was translated by Vidyasagar and the same was introduced as a textbook of Bengali (Bipin Gupta 19). Vidyasagar was convinced of the holistic superiority of the English people, Krishnakamal tells us (“সব বিষয়েই ইংরাজ শ্রেষ্ঠ”) (Bipin Gupta 26). Moreover, Vidyasagar was admired by Bengalis because he was close to the colonisers, as Krishnakamal, Vidyasagar's close disciple tells us; a sorry state of colonial power system is corroborated as Vidyasagar's perennial anxiety about his position is revealed by Krishnakamal who tells us that Vidyasagar was afraid of his possible competitors among his fellow natives who could outdo him in being a favorite of the British, and did not want any other Bengali to become close to the colonial administration (সময়ে সময়ে আশঙ্কা হইত যে, পাছে আর কোনও বাঙ্গালীর 'সাহেবদের' কাছে তাঁহার চেয়েও বেশী প্রতিপত্তি হয়) (Bipin Gupta 45). So, as a part of the government machinery, Vidyasagar was subjected to a colossal pressure of colonialism, and therefore, his position was far more complicated than Gupta, who was not on the pay of the government, or did not depend of the colonial system (of education, as in Vidyasagar's case) for livelihood.

Interestingly, Krishnakamal Bhattacharya suggests that the common indifference shown by the modern day Bengalis about Ishwar Gupta is because he was not familiar or close to the colonial government (তিনি গভর্নমেন্টের নিকট বড় একটা জানিত ছিলেন না), Bengalis being guided in their choice by western stamps of recognition; Krishnakamal Bhattacharya further observes that not a single image of Ishwar Gupta is available anywhere, owing to this lamentable indifference (Bipin Gupta 57). Anyway, to return to the matter at hand, Rosinka Chaudhuri's talk about Ishwar Gupta being a fusion is anachronistic, because a fission is yet to happen in the sensibility that Gupta represents. The rich and the poor are yet to have an insurmountable cultural gap between them in the Kolkata that Gupta, as one of the last of the Mohicans, represents. But if this fusion is conceived to be always already there, and the social cohesion (the lack of any other name for which tempts us to call it an organic integrity) with a seamless exchange of the high and the low which characterised pre-Anglicist sensibility of Bengali society, is to be dubbed as fusion, then some serious jeopardy is committed to lexicon as well as history. Fusion presupposes segregation. Now, Islamic subjugation and imposition of Persian as official language

in the middle ages could not achieve that segregation on such a grand scale what imposition of English language and culture later did. Compared to Islam's general epistemological and philosophical weakness, British colonisation went far deeper, its machinations had far-reaching consequences; Islam had Mohammad but did not have its Macaulay. It might have had its enraged Gazis (slayers of kafirs) and Jihadis (crusaders) but did not have its Enlightenment and its schools and colleges. Hegemony was to achieve what blatant coercion could not do for centuries: Bengalis were about to be subjected to the mild-altering experience of colonial modernity. Now, during Ishwar Gupta's time, this colonial process indeed begins, and that is why Gupta repeatedly laments for the loss of older forms of Bengali culture, but that process is yet to gain such momentum which is required to violently split the Bengali *gemeinschaft* (the older community, based on custom and tradition) in order to produce a contractual society of *gesellschaft*. Gupta therefore is still able to use an unfractured language and still has at his command an unfractured ethos which are not yet differentiated into the different lingoes and world-views of the enlightened-western-elites and the regressive-native-masses. Sadly, not only this impending split derails nation-consciousness to a very great extent, but it will also ensure tragic consequences for the nationalist movement in Bengal, which will never again be able to fill up in the gap between the elite bhadralks and the rustic masses. We need to be aware of this historical trajectory while studying nineteenth century Kolkata, which is subjected to an anachronistic simplification if we dub Ishwar Gupta's literary and journalistic oeuvres as fusion.

Chaudhuri also thinks of Gupta as the founder of 'everyday' in Bengali poetry (which hitherto was deprived of the quotidian) while uncritically and non-contextually reproducing a fragment from Bankim's commentary on Gupta in support of her claim: "Ishwar Gupta brought something into the Bengali language ... that was not there before him, which had given the Bengali language strength. Ishwar Gupta's poems in the *Prabhākar* showed for the first time how everyday business, political events, and social events – all this can become the subject matter of poetry" (99). Only a complete ignorance of *Kobigān* can facilitate such a statement, committing a violence against our native history, culture and heritage. Was Bankim capable of doing that? Unfortunately, Rosinka Chaudhuri misquotes Bankim here in a zeal to establish the pioneering nature of Ishwar Gupta's poems in portraying the everyday life for the *first* time in Bengali poetry, which is really what her article's argument is all about. If we investigate what Bankim originally wrote in his essay on Gupta, we see that Bankim is actually talking about *Shongbād Prabhākor* as the pioneer in foregrounding the quotidian, not Ishwar himself.

Bankim was familiar with *Kobigān* and he knew very well the inspirational influence of that genre on Gupta's poetry about everyday life. Bankim's actual statement is hereby quoted: "Routine matters, royal incidents, social incidents, that these can be subject of humorous poetry was shown for the first time by *Probhakor*. Today the Sikh war, tomorrow Poush festival, today missionary, tomorrow sycophancy, that these matters exist under the purview of literature was exhibited by none other than *Probhakor*" (711).

Ishwar Gupta was busy in running this newspaper establishment, he was running the very first Bengali daily, the foremost periodical of his days, where he eventually rose to become the editor proprietor of that venture. He encouraged new writers, and he rescued many deceased poets belonging to eighteenth and nineteenth centuries from oblivion, his being the first recorded attempt at chronicling the history of these renowned Bengali poets and *kobiwalas*, without whom modern Bengali literature would have become completely rootless. Ishwar Gupta thus intervened to impregnate his times with a nation-consciousness. As this nation-consciousness was being made in the womb of history, Ishwar Gupta became a turning point in the trajectory of the so called Hindu revival of Bengal that would flourish in the later half of nineteenth century.

Gupta's identification with Baudelaire by Rosinka Chaudhuri is no silly mistake, there is a design behind that colonising statement. This is a case of imposed significance, which characterises the reading of our texts by western parameters. The comprador intelligentsia wanted to believe in an image of itself which is at par with the west, as a measure of comforting itself into the global discourse, moving above and beyond the local in that process. The trauma of being a colony, which is *the* local as far as the Bengali experience goes, therefore must be relegated to the point from where it can no longer be assessed. Now, Chaudhuri's proposition is that Ishwar Gupta occupies a space which is similar to Baudelaire; Baudelaire was a "painter of modern life" and "here in Calcutta in the 1850s it is unmistakably Ishwar Gupta who occupies that space. Such an artist is a *flaneur*, a traveller, a cosmopolitan, but he has a loftier aim. Baudelaire says, 'he is looking for that quality which you must allow me to call 'modernity'" Chaudhuri declares, insisting on a rather unproblematic assertion of modernity in Gupta's writing (104). However, Chaudhuri begins her article by stating: "the further Bengal travelled the road of nationalist modernity, the further away it went from any understanding of, or sympathy for, the works of Iswarchandra" (87). Now, apart from the fact that nationalism never shares a linear, non-problematic, non-dialectical relationship with modernity, and therefore the simplistic use of a phrase like "nationalist modernity" can confuse and jar any reading of Bengal's complex trajectory (twisting the fact that modernity in Bengal

has been largely colonial, not nationalist), here we encounter a contradiction in Chaudhuri: Gupta is a modernist, a painter of modern life, Chaudhuri says; Chaudhuri also proposes that Gupta is undervalued and depreciated by the same modernity. Surely Chaudhuri fails to observe the real force behind the eclipse of Gupta: an increasingly pervasive colonialism, and comprador desperation to conform to the Macaulavian standards, that included Victorian prudery, snobbery, elitism and disregard for precolonial folk sensibility. While Ishwar Gupta is thought to possess inferior education by colonial standards (which counts as Gupta's demerit for all the successive ages), we notice that the bhadrakok anxiety for colonial approval which originated in the colonial times is well carried over to the 'postcolonial' times when Gupta's "uneducated" status becomes a rallying point for hostile commentators and critics. A commentator observes that though Gupta was the first to compile poet Bharatchandra's works, "it is to be doubted whether he actually understood the real meaning of Bharatchandra's poetry. He and his contemporary song-writers did not have the education, understanding, or imagination to have taken in Bharatchandra's refined and dense language, educated sensibility, easily-learned wit" (qtd. in Chaudhuri 88). Bankim himself probably started this onslaught on Gupta's inferior education with what was probably meant to be his rather sympathetic pronouncement on Gupta: "If there is one great truth that we imbibe from an analysis of Iswarchandra's life, then it is this – talent cannot reach its fullest apotheosis without good education" (qtd. in Chaudhuri 88). Bankim's scathing remarks against Ishwar Gupta in an English essay on Bengali literature (which was one of Bankim's earliest writings) are far more unkind than this, as we have already seen. Was Bankim, the first graduate of the Macaulavian University of Calcutta, here oedipally rebelling against his Guru, Ishwar Gupta? Bankim indeed speaks of Ishwar Gupta as a creditor of Bengali literature who is hurriedly forgotten by his debtors who even cease to utter his name as soon as he is gone, and Bankim counts himself as one of the debtors of Gupta (711). Now, though Bankim does not acknowledge this, but his condemnation of Gupta was surely done under the pressure of colonialism. Of course Bankim would later resist that pressure. As we have observed, one who would later compose *Vande Mataram* was the same person who once wrote about the crab like appearance of Durga and the disgusting appearance of Kali in *Rajmohan's Wife*.

Ishwarchandra Gupta's family surname was Das (Dasgupta), his parents were Horinarayon Das and Srimoti Debi, as Bankim informed us (707). Ishwar might have resorted to the surname Gupta in order to blend well with his Kolkata surroundings, as Dasgupta as a surname is totally known to be a

'Bangal' (belonging to east Bengal) surname that was not held in high esteem in western Bengal. According to Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay, Ishwarchandra Gupta was born on 6 March 1812 at Kanchrapara. He died at the age of 47 on 23 January 1859. He came to his maternal home in Kolkata at a tender age. His maternal grandfather was a friend of the Thakurs of Pathuriaghata, and he thus became friends with Jogendramohan Thakur, who was of same age as Ishwarchandra and an admirer of his poetry; their friendship lies at the root of the inception of *Shongbād Probhākor*.

Gupta's published books as recounted by Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay are:

1. *Kalikirton Grontho* by Late Ramprasad Sen. 1833.
2. *The Life of Bharatchandra* 1855.
3. *Probodh Probhakor*. 1858.
4. *Hit Probhakor*, 1861
5. *Bodhendu Bikash*, 1863.
6. *Shottonarayoner Brotokotha* 1913. (2: 738-9)

The cover of Gupta's *Life of Bharatchandra*, 1855

We can see here that half of these publications are posthumous; Gupta's journalistic work might have prevented him from authoring more book length texts. But undoubtedly, *Shongbād Probhākor* was Gupta's greatest contribution, for which alone his name deserved to be written in gold in the history of the Bengali people. Some details of this newspaper are provided by Chaudhuri:

“The *Sambād Prabhākar* was the first daily newspaper in Bengali, starting as a weekly in 1831, developing into a thrice-weekly publication from August 1836, and finally morphing into a daily from 14 June 1839. A notice at the end of the last column in the newspaper of 5 April 1849, proclaimed: 'This *Prabhākar* newspaper is published everyday excepting Sundays from house No. 44/3 situated in the lane on the southern end of the open road appearing on the south side of Calcutta's Simuliya Hendua pond. Yearly advance is valued at Rs 10.' After Iswar Gupta's death in 1859, it continued to be edited by his brother, Ramchandra Gupta, circulating till the 1880's (sic), after which it became irregular and finally ceased operations.” (92)

Probhākor published some 69 odd issues during its first phase of publication, before winding up in 1832 (Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay: 2: 173). Gupta was just 20 years old at that point of time, and he was already renowned for his poetry. The present researcher would argue that Gupta's attachment with the cultural history of his spatial domains is discernible from the fact that the three main locales of Gupta's *Kobiwalas* are Kanchrapara and adjoining areas (Gupta's native place), Jorashanko (Gupta's maternal home in Kolkata) and Shimuliya (the place of *Probhākor*'s operations). The relationship between Gupta and the cultural inheritance of Kolkata was intensely intimate, personal. Gupta's nonchalance about school education and his propensity for *Kobigān* is quit urban, and in this he is an archetypical spoilt boy (*bokhate chele*) of Kolkata who cares little for studies and freely pursues his 'lowly' interests. Gupta's project to collect and collate the works of Bengali poets starting from the late medieval writers was inaugurated in *Shongbād Probhākor* on 15 July 1854, as he issued an open appeal to his countrymen to contribute in this process of documentation. The appeal made it a collective initiative, and it turned out to be a stepping stone of nation-consciousness, with a keen sense of history, time and location.

The idea of timelessness is not exactly an invention of liberal modernity, but it has made an ample use of this idea. Certain ages are more anxious to transcend the barriers of time, and accordingly they search for that literature which is not of an age, but of all ages. The foreword to the first volume of Ishwar Gupta's collected works titled “Kobi Ishwarchandra Gupta O Bangla Shahitto” written by

Tripurashankar Senshastri begins with a customary disclaimer to this effect: Ishwar Gupta did not possess a timeless genius (“kalojoyi protibha”), the foreword diligently observes in the very first sentence (স্মৃতি). An age that is anxiously aspiring for the status of timelessness is generally the one that wants to erase its past. When Buddhism was uprooted by Brahmanism in Bengal during the eleventh century, a similar erasure of the past was done. Twentieth century Bengal, home to the Tagorean cult of universal humanism, was enamoured with the ideas of timeless truths, eternal literature, everlasting aesthetics and as a direct endeavour to impose its very own temporal standard, now promoted to an eternal status as *the* trans-historical ideal, goes on dismissing any literature that palpably defends the local and temporal concerns. Such literature is narrow, outdated, archaic. The sheer ahistoricity of this 'timeless-genius' theory is an enemy of any objective, material analysis.

Ishwar Gupta's series on the lives, times and works of the Bengali poets/songmakers consisted of biographical sketches, commentaries, collections of poems/lyrics of every individual author, and anecdotes (they were published in the literary supplement of *Shongbād Probhākor*, and this last component betrayed a journalistic style of writing). In his essay on Bharatchandra, quite significantly Gupta castigates the colonial present, and longingly, nostalgically speaks of the pre-British times, lamenting for the loss of an organic past:

“The times when we have been born as humans have been our undoing, our termination. These times on behalf of our British rulers (the shorthand for British used by Gupta is 'the Red coloured', রক্তাঙ্গ) became giant wings spread out to extinguish the light of this swarthy country. Where is that freedom? Where is that happiness? Where is that ethics (dharma)? Where is that work (karma)? Where is that knowledge? Where is that driving force? Where is that scholarship? Where is that spirit of poetry? Where is that appreciation? Where is that honour? And where is that enthusiasm, that passion? With the murder of freedom, time has devoured everything.” (1: 8)

It is pertinent to observe here that Ishwar Gupta is not speaking of the loss of freedom of the Hindus following the Muslim conquest in the remote past. He does not displace the current trauma of colonisation in the manner of Bankim to the Islamic conquest. He categorically evokes the time of Raja Krishnachandra of Nadia as the age of freedom, thereby paradoxically portraying a time when Hindus had been 'independent', not subjugated by the British (this is paradoxical on two counts: first, Hindus really had a limited freedom because Bengal at that point of time was under the rule of a Muslim

Nawab and secondly, Krishnachandra was one of the main architects of the cessation of the rule of Siraj which heralded the rule of the British; in other words, Raja Krishnachandra himself brought about the downfall of this so-called freedom which Ishwar Gupta discovers in the Raja's golden, exemplary rule prior to the advent of western domination). Gupta laments the loss of an age when Bengalis were free and wrote such poetry as befitted a free people which they now no longer can write as the present times have deprived them of that freedom which is a necessary condition for all substantial creations, according to Gupta. The collection of the poetry of his predecessors is full of his sighs for a lost age to which those poets belonged.

Gupta was not having an exceptional, isolated, uncharacteristic bout of anti-colonial feeling here. Utpal Dutt in his *Girish Manosh* is full of praise for Gupta's anti-British satirical poetry, ostensibly commemorating the ascension of Queen Victoria to the throne of India, written from the perspective of the Bengali native subjects, who are compared to *posha goru* (domesticated cows), who not being able to tolerate an odd punch, kick or blow, will be happy to chew fodder (31). Gupta indeed wrote some poems celebrating British victory over India, but, that might have owed to a pressure from his subscribers, saying which of course does not absolve him of the charge of compradorship. Gupta's brazen support for the British in the aftermath of the great rebellion of 1857 in his poems has drawn many criticisms. Bengali educated classes in different parts of India unanimously sided with the British. Calcutta Babus being the rank and pillar of British civil administration were caught in the vortex of 1857, as it has entered into the folklore of Sepoy mutiny, the rebel Sepoys used to attack, and often imprison Bengali Babus after they were done with the British (Joshi branchcollective.org, Husain xxx). Under such circumstances, Ishwar Gupta had to cater to the sentiments of these Calcutta Babus, many of them readers of *Shongbād Probhākor*: “The diasporic Bengalis living in northern and western India were subscribers of *Probhākor* and they regularly sent updates about local important matters. During the Sepoy Mutiny these correspondents rendered a special service to *Probhākor*” (Bankim 712).

A celebration of Kolkata as the archetypical expression of Bengaliness is very often indistinguishable from a celebration of the empire in the literary and cultural products of the nineteenth century. Rupchand *Pokkhi*'s renowned song about Kolkata is a case in point (fully reproduced in Patrea 9-14). It begins with a chant of 'glory to the city of Kolkata', and calls Kolkata a celestial city ('elder sibling of heaven'). Then the song rapidly degrades into a catalogue of the achievements of the British. This celebrated song comes across as a piece of sycophancy at worst, and public relation for the white

rulers at best when we read it today. But Bengali identity in making was in many respects a contribution of the newfound position of significance which Bengalis enjoyed under the British, following the successful conspiracy leading to the removal of the last Muslim sovereign of Bengal. Gupta's defence of the British must be seen in this respect. Upper and middle class Bengalis thrived as an ally of the British during this period which was yet to witness any major clash of interests between them. It is interesting to note that a general current of Anglicisation led Rupchand *Pokkhi* to always give his name as R. C. Bird, i.e. Roop Chund Bird as the editor's foreword in Bipin Gupta's *Puraton Proshongo* informs us (সতের).

The trauma over a loss of the past is integral to all major revival movements, as the history of Irish revival also attests. Ishwar Gupta attributes a want of historical sense among the Bengalis to the lack of record-keeping and unavailability of biographies of the great people born in Bengal. An elated reader's letter to *Shongbād Probhākor* observes that Ishwar Gupta's initiative will bring the great poet-singer Ramprasad (creator of devotional songs of Kali known as Shyamashongee) to the purview of Nobbo Shomproday (New Society, a shorthand for the westernised Bengalis) who were hitherto ignorant of him (*Collected Works* 1: 25). The same letter also painstakingly and anachronistically attempts to establish Ramprasad's credentials as the worshipper of a single godhead, rather in the vein of Brahmo elitism, Kali being a mere name for that godhead (the letter writer goes on to muse: what is in a name after all, and a rose being called by any other name would smell just as sweet). Ramprasad's evocation of Kali is little more than a mere lip service to idolatry, the letter observes (1: 26-27). Ishwar Gupta himself later states: whom the non-idolatrous worships under the name of Brahma, Ramprasad worships the same God under the name of Kali (1:40).

Ramprasad Sen

A deflection of our own heritage of Shakto worship is thus consciously or unconsciously undertaken by Ishwar Gupta. But this deflection is not without benefits to the nation-making, as Gupta's attempt of consolidation is apparent in his identification of idolatrous Kali of the Hindu masses with the non-idolatrous Brahma of the Brahmo elites. As Gupta stated what Ramprasad Sen worshipped as Kali was what the Brahmos worshipped as Brahma (1: 13), he was pursuing coordination.

North Kolkata, near the renowned temple of Chitteshshori, from whom Chitpur derived its name. James Baillie Fraser, 1826

However, Gupta's project is also marked by a sense of urgency, as the rapid erosion of the old society caused by the advancement of colonialism made it increasingly difficult to carry out the process of documenting the past. Gupta speculated that in another five years all records of the works of these poets would be lost as the ancient people who still were alive and could offer testimonies and manuscripts and transcripts from memory would be no more, and the contemporary young men coming out of western education system would have been forever deprived of this legacy (1: 56). Gupta appeals to the “Nobbo Shobhbho Shomproday” (New Civil Society, the westernised elites) to read the lives and works of the old poets in order to appreciate the wealth of Bengali language and literature (1: 56-57). While giving the details of the mechanism of patronage which helped the old poets survive and thrive in society, Ishwar Gupta clearly desired a similar mechanism in nineteenth century Kolkata. Evidently, Gupta who himself was dependent on the vagaries of market and other interest lobbies looked back longingly at the older patron-poet relationships and networks: “Oh! What pleasurable times that were lost. Now that King Krishnachandra is no more, that patron-encourager, that fortune's favourite is no more, that Bharatchandra is no more, that Ramprasad Sen is no more, Anything of their kind is no more to be found.

This age now is a false age.” (1: 76). We should ask ourselves here: is Ishwar Gupta a writer who remains obsessively confined to whatever he finds around him? Is he just a poet of *jaha aache* as Bankim put it so eloquently? Reading Gupta's works convinces us otherwise.

Here it is important to note that Gupta's collection of lives and works of Bengali poets is not a hagiography; for example, he is fairly critical of Bharatchandra's renowned mongolkabbo *Onnodamongol* which, as Gupta says, lacks in most of the nine classical *rasas* except that of the erotic (*Shirngāra rasa*), with a little bit of heroic (*veera rasa*) thrown in to compensate; *Onnodamongol* is a testimony to Bharatchandra's scholarship, knowledge, diligence and care, while it also exposes a lack of what Gupta thinks as divine, creative inspirational force (1: 85-86). Ishwar Gupta's chosen dimensions of space which defined these poets-predecessors clearly reflect a larger pattern of the pre-British civilisational heritage that went into the making of Kolkata. The location of Bharatchandra is crucial here, as Gupta puts it: “The king asked: Which place under my dominion that is stretched from Nabadwip to Kolkata do you wish to inhabit?” (1: 68). The king in this sentence is Krishnachandra, and the “you” in this sentence is poet Bharatchandra, who comes to choose Mulajor as his preferred place of residence (modern day Shyamnagar on the Ganges, 25 km from Kolkata). Bharatchandra's origin is traced back to Burdwan, while he flourished in Krishnanagar in the royal court of King Krishnachandra and settled to live in Mulajor, thus moving progressively closer to Kolkata. This is not consciously suggested, but a careful reader can decipher in this trajectory the epicentre shifting slowly to Kolkata as if in a cultural-historical mapping which governs Ishwar Gupta's literary unconscious. Further, Ramprasad Sen lived at Kumarhotto, (modern day Haliashahar on the Ganges, not far from Shymnagar again). This must be mentioned that these areas are not very far from Ishwar Gupta's own birth place at Kanchrapara on the Ganges. They constitute a common cluster.

Ramnidhi Gupta, more popularly known as Nidhubabu, during his childhood was reared at Kumartuli, Kolkata. He is the third poet whom Ishwar Gupta discusses after Ramprasad and Bharatchandra. With Ramnidhi, Ishwar not just comes to Kolkata proper, he also delves into the subject of eighteenth century Bengali songs which included various popular and urbane forms like *Kobigān*. In connection with Ramnidhi, Ishwar speaks of the *Pokkhis*, a close-knit countercultural movement of intoxicated singers, heavy smokers of cannabis who dressed to appear like birds and spoke in a cooing manner (hence the name, *Pokkhi*). A place at Shobhabajar was the favourite den of the *Pokkhis* which

was also frequented by Ramnidhi, who as a singer was much admired by the *Pokkhis* (1: 89-90). Ishwar Gupta offers a very lively sketch of the *Pokkhis'* ways of life in connection with the biography of Ramnidhi. It is quite interesting to note that the wealthy patron of Ramnidhi as well as the *Pokkhis* named Ramchandra Mitra, the *aatchala* (arena with a typical eight-sided roof as can be seen in Bengal's temple architecture) of whose Shobhabajar residence used to host these musical soirées, amassed his riches by virtue of being an “agent of an American Captain” (1: 89-90). The comprador economy of Bengal is seen to be capable of promotion of Bengali culture, provided the latter does not clash in any immediate manner with the former.

Ishwar Gupta ventures into a brief sketch of *Ākhrāi* songs, the main proponent-practitioner of that genre being Ramnidhi Gupta's maternal uncle Kului Chandra Sen (1: 91). Ramnidhi had his own foray into *Ākhrāi* music; he had organised an *Ākhrāi* competition between two teams, belonging to Bagbajar and Shobhabajar respectively, where he himself composed music and lyric for the Bagbajar team, the lead singer of which was Mohonchand Bose. This event took place in the Bengali year 1211 (1: 91). Later, a more popular version of *Ākhrāi* developed by Ramnidhi's close associate Mohonchand Bose came to be known as half-*Ākhrāi* (1: 92). While Ishwar Gupta was writing this article, Mohonchand was still alive, and was a living legend, albeit in frail health, a shadow of his former self. Interestingly, one of the major differences between the formats of *Ākhrāi* and half-*Ākhrāi* seems to be that in the former genre, the singer stands in the fashion of *Kobigān* which is also performed by standing poets (দাঁড়া কবি) (though *Ākhrāi* did not employ an exchange of challenges and replies in the vein of *Kobigān* and here victory and defeat were solely determined by popular verdict on the performance of the teams), while in half-*Ākhrāi* the singer actually seats in the fashion of *Toppa* (1: 93). *Toppa* was the form of music pioneered by Ramnidhi Gupta which revolutionised Bengali songs and even today, after two hundred years, the genre is fondly sung and heard. Given the sad demise of *Ākhrāi* – it was already dead for thirty years by the time Gupta was writing his essay (1: 95) – as well as the passing away of *Kobigān*, *Pānchāli*, *Pokkhi* and most other forms of our indigenous music, the survival of *Toppa* is significant.

Ishwar Gupta's choice of the first three poets in this series on the poets and songmakers of the past age is indeed significant, as the works of these three have survived the weathering of time; Ramprasad's devotional songs addressed to Ma Kali (Shyamashongee), Bharatchandra's text *Onnodamongol* and Ramnidhi's *Toppa* have managed to interest Bengalis steadily throughout the

modern period. They still strike a chord because the creations of these three writers have gone into the making of the cultural legacy of the Bengalis of Kolkata. Otherwise, the steady loss of older forms of entertainments as time and mentality change is an inevitable fact of cultural history that Ishwar Gupta bemoans (1: 95), and in that context, we may observe that Gupta's project of coordiNation has succeeded to a certain extent. He instilled a love for some of these older forms of Bengali poetry in the mind of the increasingly westernised Bengalis as the Bengal Renaissance was about to dawn, and Gupta ensured that they would never again be lost by making their appeal discernible for the newly ascendant class of university educated Bengalis. The pre-colonial roots of a colonised people were restored, never again to be easily lost.

Interestingly, Brahma movement seems to have encouraged a seamless exchange between *Ākhrāi* and its own devotional repertoire. Gupta observes that a noted singer of *Ākhrāi* was also a regular performer of Brohmoshongeet at Rammohan Roy's meetings (1:94), whereas the formless (*nirakara*) unitary god of the Brahmos became a topic of the *Ākhrāi* songs (1: 93-94). It shows that the popularity of this medium of *Ākhrāi* was such that the Brahma movement felt a need to appropriate it, whereas *Ākhrāi* too felt a necessity to align itself to the intellectual and philosophical currents of Brahmaism, which became prevalent in the educated society. *Ākhrāi* had a geographical trajectory that once more exhibited a movement towards the epicentre of Kolkata: it originated at Shantipur, then it started being performed at Chinsurah; performers from Chinsurah used to come to Kolkata's Burrabazar (Borobajar) for *Ākhrāi* soirées at the floral garden (*phoolbagan*) of a rich patron named Kashinath, Gupta informs (1:103). Eventually, Jorashanko of Kolkata became a centre for *Ākhrāi* music, with its own local breed of performers. Later, Shyampukur also boasted of the honour of an *Ākhrāi* team of its own. This Kolkata-bound movement of *Ākhrāi* also changed its generic format; the original version performed in Shantipur had two segments, namely *Kheur* (argument) and *Probhati* (of the morning) but Chinsurah and Kolkata teams of *Ākhrāi* added an introductory part which sang of the subject of Durga (*Bhobani bishoy*). Further, *Ākhrāi* was purged of those elements which were considered to be uncouth, rustic and obscene as it moved towards an urban, metropolitan sensibility, which is evident in Gupta's commentary (1: 103). This is obvious that Kolkata tended to move away from all folk rusticity, as the city strove for sophistication and a certain bhadrlokisation. Ishwar Gupta appreciates that tendency, not realising that his own poetry will later fall victim to that very trend as his poetry will fall short of the suave standards of colonial urbanity, Bankim's adverse comments coming immediately to mind.

Committing the entire oral tradition of Bengali music into writing, haunted by a sense of urgency on the face of a quickly vanishing past that is becoming increasingly difficult to be accessed by the colonised Bengalis, Ishwar Gupta's oeuvre is marked by a tension, an apprehension: Gupta repeatedly says that with the possible impending demise of all the old timers, Bengal will be forever impoverished, deprived of its heritage (1: 107). Gupta is worried that the new, westernised generation will forever remain misinformed about the glorious heritage of Bengali music and poetry if this project is not carried out and past works are not retrieved:

“How can some young men, who, with practising western knowledge and western poetics have only learnt western connoisseurship, be appreciative towards Bengali poetry? Because they have no cultivation (অনুশীলন), they have not heard anything. They scoff at and dislike (Bengali poems and songs) upon hearing a vulgar poem or two in marketplaces from mere actors. Therefore we cannot accuse the new lot (*Nobbogon*) as callous, because how they can (be expected to) appreciate unacquainted matters” (1: 109).

Gupta expresses his hope that once the westernised youth of his day gets a glimpse of this treasure of Bengali music, the attitude of indifference (or that of contempt) will yield to that of an appreciation of tradition. Here he is concerned about *Kobigān* in this particular statement.

The so called lower castes played a huge role in the performance and reception of this genre, whereas the rich classes, comprising of upper and lower castes alike, patronised *kobigān*. Ishwar Gupta rescued *Kobiwala* Gonjla Guin from oblivion, who belonged to the lower stratum of society. Ishwar Gupta attempted to retrieve this tradition of *Kobigān* which had Guin at its origin, while this chiefly oral tradition was at a substantial risk of being forever lost. Sadly, the twentieth century Hungryalists, masquerading their westernisation in the guise of subaltern sensibility, did not even care to mention Ishwar Gupta in their revolutionary proclamations involving the name of Gonjla Guin and other *Kobiwalas* (Nachiketa Bandyopadhyay 190-191). Gupta informed us: “It had been 140 or 150 years since Gonjla Guin set up his professional troupe that used to sing at the soirées held at the residences of rich people;” Guin left behind three pupils: Lalunondolal who lived at Forashdanga (Chandannagar), Roghu and Ramji; Horu Thakur was a disciple of Roghu, Bhubane Bene of Ramji and Nitey Boishnob of Lalunondolal; further, Keshta Muchi (a cobbler by caste) was a fearsome opponent and defeated Horu Thakur (who was a Brahman) a number of times (1:109). The origin of *Kobigān* is traced back to Gonjla

Guin by Gupta, who offers his obeisance to Guin in these words: “O Guin, were you a mere human being? One whose expanse is like that of the cosmos, is named Gonjla (the term means a pint of alcohol)! Can one measure this pint (Gonjla) with a palm's offering (Aanjla)?” (1: 110). This work of collecting old Bengali poetry was a work more difficult than meditation on a corpse (*Shob Shadhon*), according to Gupta, who interviewed more than two hundred odd old-timers for this project (1: 111). It is indeed a measurement of the deflection of nation-consciousness of the Bengali people that the Hungryalists have been allowed to make a song and dance about the *Kobiwalas* of Bengal, lifting them straight from Gupta's works without bothering to acknowledge this man's hard labour. Surely, Gupta did not suit the temperament of the westernised intelligentsia, and he had to be assigned to oblivion.

The life of *Kobiwala* Ram Basu once more depicts the Kolkata-bound movement. He was born in the village of Shalikhia (modern day Shalkia) of Howrah district, and as a child came to Jorashanko to live with Banarasi Ghosh, his uncle (pishemoshai), Gupta tells us (1: 111). He was a lyricist and wrote for many noted *Kobiwalas* (including Bhobane Bene, Nilu Thakur, Mohon Sorkar, Thakurdas Singha) since his early adolescence, before coming to don the hat of *Kobiwala* himself, launching his own troupe of *Kobigān*. Later, under his tutelage, a troupe of *Kobigān* also came into existence at Bhowanipore which regularly performed his songs. Ram Basu died at the premature age of forty two, while Ishwar Gupta highly praises Ram, bestowing upon him a crowning glory among all *Kobiwalas*: “What Kalidasa is to Sanskrit Poetry, what Bharat Chandra and Ram Prasad are to Bengali poetry, Ram Basu is to the poetry of *Kobiwalas*” (1: 113).

Ram Basu died in the Bengali year 1235/1236, Gupta tells us; Basu returned in ill health after performing at the Durgapujo held in the residence of Raja Harinath Ray of Murshidabad (1: 112). This brief information probably tells us two important things. First, Kolkata was steadily emerging as a beacon for the districts which looked forward to hearing from the songmakers of Kolkata, as the districts got directly exposed to the culture of Kolkata. Kolkata artists performing in districts thus begins as a steady cultural practice, particularly during Durgapujo festivities. Secondly, while the rich people constantly patronised him, Ram Basu was probably over-exhausted owing to the demands placed on him by the lovers of *Kobigān*, and that such performances probably took a toll on his health. Gupta further observes that since the death of Ram Basu, no one is enamoured of hearing the songs of the *Kobiwalas* anymore (1:130). While discussing Ram Basu, Gupta takes good care to include the life and works of some of his renowned contemporaries: Rasu Nrishingho, Horu Thakur, Nilu Thakur, Nitaidas Boiragi (1: 130-131).

He thus effectively records that milieu in which a plethora of talents flourished during a period which was the peak of the art-form of *Kobigān*.

Durgapujo at the residence of a wealthy Bengali. James Prinsep, 1840.

As Gupta was carrying out his project, he was also being engulfed in that movement of colonial urbanity which will very soon claim himself as a casualty. Colonisation was an ongoing process. This was the big crunch, here was the formation of the metropolis as its periphery broadened and the ever expanding city continued to swallow its villages. Folk sensibility continued to shrink as the colonial city enlarged. This happened in terms of space, and in terms of history and culture. Exemplifying that colonial progress, Nirad C Chaudhuri in the twentieth century ridicules the remnants of rural superstition among the people of Kolkata:

“In the narrow lanes of Calcutta were to be found, surviving and spinning out an unnatural existence, rituals and beliefs, practices and superstitions, ... The people of Calcutta worshipped the “Goddess of No Prosperity” together with the Goddess of Prosperity; they worshipped the Goddess of Skin Disease and of Cholera; the Goddess of Smallpox was one of their major deities. Their menfolk (sic) were extremely afraid of going into the water closet with their hair let down, and they always tied its ends in a knot before going in, because they believed the W.C.s to be the favourite haunts of evil spirits who would possess them unless their hair was up.” (402-403).

The Enlightenment haughtiness with which Nirad C. pokes fun at Olokkhi (Goddess of No Prosperity) and Lokkhi (Goddess of Prosperity), Goddess of Cholera (OlaiChondi) and Goddess of Smallpox (Shitola), though he does not mention the original Bengali names of these goddesses, is a characteristically male and imperial denigration of one's own native Shakto heritage. Nirad C. wants to make it doubly disreputable, and therefore conjures up a separate Goddess of Skin Disease, whereas Bengalis only have a Goddess of Smallpox, Shitola, whose history by the way is more than a thousand years old and is at least traced back to the Buddhist period. Further, imposition of *Western* standards often resulted in dubious systems of analysis. WC of the west cannot be compared to the Indian style toilets, which were often a long walk from one's house, invariably always outside one's main residence (owing to reasons of purity), usually at the periphery of one's premises, under the open sky, very often near bushes and woods, fit places for imagining the haunting of ghosts. Nirad's imposition of the yardstick of WC on Indian style toilets only serves to condemn our cultural realities.

Another depiction of Chitpur, the typical Bengali Kolkata, with the temple on the background. Charles D'Oyly, 1830.

Kolkata, as the second city of the empire was encouraged to lose its own identity, tradition and history in a deluge of colonialism. Ishwar Gupta is fighting against that tide which is about to claim himself as its prey, but before that, he is capable of doing his bit: he resuscitates Bengal's forgotten glory of *Kobigān*. And he is doing this precisely at a time when Bengal's past is getting violently uprooted

owing to the machinations of colonialism: Gupta laments that even those cultural forms which were prevalent only 20 or 30 years ago are getting lost nowadays, with no hopes for retrieval, and the young Bengalis are being forever deprived of the glorious legacy of *Kobigān*. He reiterates that unless young people are acquainted with the nuances of these indigenous cultural forms, appreciation of these art forms is not possible (1: 131). However, at times Gupta voice resonates with the certainty and confidence of a seer; “henceforth these poets will roam immortal in the world,” he proclaims with an authority after publishing the collections of the lives and works of these pre-British Bengali poets (1:182). Further, we should note that as he recorded the chronicle of Bengali poetry of seventeenth, eighteenth and nineteenth century, he was acting as a connoisseur, as an insider, not just as a conservationist, which is evident everywhere in his commentary on these poets. He considered it a pilgrimage, not a painstaking task. Committing oral traditions to written discourse is of singular importance as nation-consciousness begins to assume definite shapes and forms, and Gupta's contribution in this regard is Promethean. One oral song after another comes to him in incomplete and fragmentary shapes, but Gupta never gives up, and he renews his requests to all old-timers to come forward and help in this project with whatever that can be excavated from their memory.

Nitai Boiragi was born in the Bengali year 1158 at Chandannagar, south of Chuchura. His main songwriter Gour Kobiraj was an inhabitant of Shimulia (Shimla) of Kolkata, and Gour Kobiraj was a regular writer for a number of other *Kobiwalas*, including Lokey Jugi (Lokkhikanto, who was a Jugi by caste) and Nilu Thakur. Nitai Boiragi was called by his ardent followers Probhu Nityananda (after the name of Nityananda, the legendary religious leader and social reformer of the Boishnob movement), and Gupta notes that his sphere of influence included Kumarhotto, Bhatpara, Kanchrapara, Tribeni, Bali, Forashdanga and Chuchura (1: 167). These locales (which include Gupta's own native place Kachrapara) speak of a cultural map that went into the making of Kolkata. The fact that Nitai too met the same way of death as Ram Basu did (he returned ill from a performance during Durgapujo at the house of the king of Kashimbajar and died eventually) (1: 167), speaks volumes about the predicament of a *Kobiwala* and the crisis of the cultural practice of *Kobigān* which was an absolutely exhaustive performing art, with a requirement of a tremendous amount of mental and physical labour.

Coordination as a project in order to be carried out needed the best possible contributions from Gupta's countrymen, who once lamented that his project could succeed only if there was a synthesis of “the intellect of the Bengalis and the physical strength of the *Khotta* (a derogatory Bengali term for the

people from the part of upper India including modern day Bihar and UP who are considered to be physically robust), riches of the wealthy and the mindset of an enthusiast” on the part of the Bengali people (1: 181). Not to be deterred by difficulties, Gupta continued to chronicle the literary history of *Kobigān*. Renowned *Kobiwalas* Rasu and Nrishingho were brothers, who lived at a village near Forashdanga. They performed together (hence their names were always taken together as Rasu Nrishingho, as if they were one) and were contemporaneous with or slightly senior to Horu Thakur, as Gupta records (1: 183). Lokey Kana (not to be confused with Lokey Jugi) was another renowned *Kobiwala* based at Thonthon, Kolkata. His real name was Lokkhikanto Biswas, he was an excellent composer and singer, he specialised in *Pānchāli*, and according to Gupta he was renowned as a great humorist. Legendarily ready-witted, he was frequently compared with Gopal Bhanr (1: 207). His main opponent was Ganganarayan Naskar of Shobhabajar. Lokkhikanto was admired by his wealthy patrons who also feared the sharpness of his wit. He was survived by his son Boiddonath who carried on his troupe, and still later Lokkhikanto's grandson (by his daughter) Dorponarayan continued that tradition; he died some thirty five years before Gupta was recording Lokkhikanto's life and works (1: 209). Gupta refrains from reproducing Lokkhikanto's most works because of the high frequency of obscene words in them; Gupta uses the words profane (অপবিত্র), unchaste (অসাম্মু) to describe Lokey Kana's lyrics (1: 207-208).

Ishwar Gupta while tracing a history of *Kobiwalas* gives us valuable insights into the cultural environment of the old, traditional Kolkata and adjoining districts of south Bengal. The fact that he himself belonged to this region which was now forming the nucleus of a consolidated Bengali identity and ushering the Bengali revival is significantly aligned with Gupta's project: he is a native inhabitant of this region which now serves as the epicentre of Bengal's nation-consciousness, and it gives him an insider's privilege in collecting the lost chronicles of these Bengali poets at the risk of being completely forgotten as colonial modernity continues its triumphant march. Consistent with Gupta's cultural mapping, Horu Thakur was a native of Kolkata's Shimulia again, and like a majority of other *Kobiwalas* he was neither educated in English or Sanskrit, nor he was particularly decent by the Victorian standards which was increasingly becoming the norm of the day in Ishwar Gupta's Kolkata. Gupta's collection therefore had to censor and suppress some segments of *Kobigān* which are not commensurate with imperial civilisational standards. Gupta says:

“But the sad part is that some too debased, too hated, non-audible, unspeakable words used to fill (their poetry), therefore publishing them is not legitimate. ... Earlier our most exalted noblemen, that included Maharaja Krishnachandra, Nobokrishno and others used to be very satisfied with such peculiar slangs (Sho-kar, Bo-kar, as Gupta puts it; in Bengali that means unspeakable vulgar expletives, mostly beginning with Sh and B), their entertainment having no bounds. Surrounded by cousins, relatives, kinsmen, good people, they heard with glad minds.” (1: 190).

Gupta adds in the same breath that Raja Nabakrishna was an ardent admirer of Horu Thakur whereas Krishnachandra's favourite was Lochon Khorki of Shantipur. It is significant that Gupta extensively speaks on Horu, but Lochon Khirki of Shantipur finds just a cursory mention, proving that Kolkata and its surroundings are being privileged in his discourse. Further, here Ishwar Gupta is seen to be completely affected by the current standards of decency, calling those parts of *Kobigān* obscene which do not conform to those standards, thus purging those elements out of his chronicles which embarrass the imperial metropolitan sensibility.

We have seen that the elitist cult of Victorian prudery wreaked havoc in the field of culture. Bengali *Kobigān* came to be consigned to the wasteland of history by stalwarts like Tagore. Further, there was manipulation, censoring and complete overhauling of lyrics in order to secure respectability and acceptance. Comprador classes were eager to conform to the standards provided by colonial masters. One interesting example of this bhadrakalok manipulation of texts can be found if we compare the texts of the *Kobir Lorai* (Battle of Poetry, the standard competition in public between two rival *Kobiwalas*) between Bhola Moyra and Anthony Firingi as recorded by Kalidas Ray's *Prachin Bongo Shahitto* and Purna Chandra Dey's work on Anthony. With the recent republication of Purna Chandra Dey Udbhatsagar's text, *Kobi Anthony Shaheb*, this *Kobir Lorai* has been depicted in numerous stage adaptations and films which are made on the life of Anthony. Now, there is a place where Bhola responds to Anthony, saying that Anthony is confusing him with Lord Bholanath (Lord Shiva) and Bhola says (in Purna Chandra's version): “If I am that Bholanath, then why it is so that everyone searches for the feet of Bholanath, but never searches for my feet (to pay obeisance)?” This line also featured in the lyric of Uttam Kumar-starrer *Anthony Firingi*. Interestingly, Kalidas Ray omits this particular line (that follows “If I am that Bholanath), saying that this part was obscene (667). It seems that Purnachandra Dey provided an altered version, because there is no obscenity there. There is no way we can know for sure

how that 'obscene' line went originally. Though, this is probable that the original version somehow went like this: If I am that Bholanath, then why it is so that everyone searches for the *phallus (lingo)* of Bholanath, but never searches for my *phallus* (to pay obeisance)? Further, the next four lines which follow are provided in Ray's work but find no mention anywhere else, as these lines, belonging to the segment of *Kheur* (quarrel) where the *Kobiwalas* attacked each other in expletives with some élan and gusto, were also indecent by the bhadrakok standards. Now, this is one example where a Bhadrakok sensibility is successful in deflecting an original lyric which now exists only in the manipulated version and can now only be heard within the colonially approved format of decency.

Exchange between Anthony Firingi (UttamKumar) and Bhola Moyra (AsitBaran). A still from *Anthony Firingi* (1967)

Owing to UttamKumar's stellar performance, Bengalis think of Anthony Firingi whenever they hear a mention of *Kobigān*

Nineteenth century Kolkata, as *the* colonial city, was subjected to a “sweeping imperial sense of metropolitan enormity” (Hunt 187). It was inside this enormity of a colonial headquarter that Ishwar Gupta was producing a native cultural counterweight by running the first vernacular daily in the subcontinent, where he tried to foster a sense of native rootedness, which later acted as the strongest motif in the Bengali renaissance. Gupta's project of coordination is about recovering an identity that one can call one's own. Gupta wanted to rescue the traditional identity and culture of this city that was increasingly at a risk of being devoured and appropriated (which these days is suitably glorified as hybridity and fusion and cultural dialogue in liberal-humanist parlance) in a Macaulavian manner that ominously resonates throughout Hunt's book: “Kipling himself had once written of Calcutta, 'Why, this is London! This is the docks. This is Imperial. This is worth coming across India to see!’” (189). The city called Calcutta was the headquarter of British India and was in the vortex of 'modernity' which increasingly became synonymous with a steady loss of heritage: “attorney William Hickey commented on how during the 1770s the old Bengal style of mud houses was 'being replaced by well-constructed solid masonry' (Hunt 198). Further, “a fiercely Enlightenment notion of progress and improvement, crucial to European self-approbation, was evident in the development of Calcutta. Out of the dense jungle of Bengal and the thick swamps of the Hooghly there arose a glistening tribute to Western civilization protected by the might of Fort William” (Hunt 198). Now, this myth has been perpetuated *ad nauseum* thanks to a certain amnesia on the part of the gullible Bengalis, who would always readily come to believe that Kolkata rose out of barren lands, that it rose out of jungle and swamps. Our colonisers wanted this impression, that nothing at all existed here immediately prior to their arrival. Whatever past glories that India could boast of must be suitably pushed back to ancient times (owing to the Aryan invasion theory, the British too could bask in the glory of ancient India). Colonialism justifies itself precisely on these terms of an *a priori* blankness or backwardness of the colonised people.

While “in Calcutta, there took place a sustained process of cultural Anglicization” (Hunt 219), the attempt to justify the violation of Bengali cultural traditions also came in a packaging of plurality and multiculturalism, cross-cultural dialogue and coexistence of communities. Liberalism never fails to serve the long-term purposes of imperialism in a colony. Sample this statement: “Calcutta was, like Cape Town, an expressly multicultural city. 'Chinese and Frenchmen, Persians and Germans, Arabs and Spaniards, Armenians and Portuguese, Jews and Dutchmen, are seen mixing with the Hindoos and English, the original inhabitants and the actual possessors of the country,' as Maria Graham recounted it” (Hunt 202).

Multicultural Kolkata is home to everybody, with no superior claim or priority of the Bengalis. As colonial standards preside over this multicultural domain, effectively the status quo of the most powerful principle of domination (that of colonial authority) remains supreme, because any indigenous power can never challenge that authority by staking its own claim to rule its own land without in fact unsettling the fundamental premises of multiculturalism. Acceptance of this multiculturalism is habitually done by a bhadralok liberal-humanist sensibility that remained one of the most potent factors behind the deferral of nation-consciousness.

However, as opposed to the multicultural and cosmopolitan Kolkata, there was another Kolkata that was not embarrassed of its Bengali characteristics. Gupta was rooted in the native (and not the multicultural) Kolkata. Bankim wrote about an anecdote that relates to Ishwar Gupta's childhood years in Kolkata's Jorashanko. It consists a rhyme of two lines that later acquired a legendary status:

It is said that when Ishwar Gupta was three years old, once he fell ill after coming to his maternal home in Kolkata. He was bed ridden in that illness. Kolkata in those days used to be quite unhealthy, and there was too much menace of mosquitoes and flies. A bed ridden Ishwar Gupta one day composed and recited the following

Mosquitoes by night, flies by day

Shooing these in Kolkata I stay

(রেতে মশা দিনে মাছি

এই তাড়য়ে কলকাতায় আছি)

Really? Many may not believe this – we don't know whether to believe or not. But since the legend about John Stuart Mill learning Greek at the age of three has spread throughout the world of letters, then let this word have its spread too. (708).

Now, Gupta's childhood composition was a typical nineteenth century celebration of native Kolkata, in the midst of all the dirt and drudgery. It could well have been a characteristic piece from the genre of *Kobigān*. Indeed Gupta's proficiency in this genre was noticed by people around him during his childhood. Bankim extensively quotes from a letter written by a childhood friend of Ishwar Gupta published after Gupta's death, in the *Shongbād Probhākor* Literary supplement of 1 Boishakh 1266 Bengali Year, which informs us of the following:

1. That Gupta, when he was 11/12 years old, started doing extempore composition for professional

teams of *Kobiwalas* when they came to perform at Kanchonpolli (original name of Kanchrapara).

2. That Gupta was always a gifted poet, and could easily compose verse since early childhood.

3. That he was a *shrutidhor*, which means he could remember whatever he heard just once. It is pointed out by Gupta's childhood friend that Gupta could remember all Bengali poems which he heard, and he had a pictorial memory, which used to capture words forever in its canvass.

4. That he was a good student (now, this is a curious point, given that he did not complete any formal education), and on his own initiative he mastered entire Sanskrit grammar (*Mugdhobodh*) in one and half month flat, at the age of seventeen (Bankim 709).

“Gentoo Pagoda and House” of Chitpur by Thomas Daniel, 1787. Contrast the cleanliness, hygiene and prosperity of this 'native' Kolkata with the ones painted by Fraser (1826) and D'Oyly (1830). It exposes the fact (otherwise carefully overlooked) that British colonisation impoverished and degraded the Bengali parts of Kolkata

It seems that Gupta was a prodigy, and that the responsibility of recovering Bengaliness from the onslaught of colonialism was in able hands. Ishwar Gupta died at a premature age of 47, as if finishing his jobs early imposed an early retirement on him. A new scene was about to begin, and it is as if Gupta went away from the stage to make way for the new actors who would now occupy centrestage and limelight in Kolkata. One of Gupta's early jobs was the founding of *Shongbād Probhākor* in 1831, when he was just nineteen years old. Jogendramohan Thakur of the Pathuriaghata Thakur family was of same age and was Ishwar's close friend and patron. It was Jogendramohan who funded *Shongbād Probhākor* as it was published for the first time in the Bengali Year 1237 (1831 CE).

Bankim in his essay on Ishwar Gupta called this collaboration between Jogendramohan and Ishwar Gupta as an alliance between Lokkhi and Shoroshshoti, i.e. wealth and creativity (710). Ishwar Gupta's account of the history of Shongbād Probhākor (published in the issue of 1 Boishakh 1253) informs us that this venture as it was founded was completely dependent on Jogendramohan for finance (qtd. in Bankim 710). Prior to *Probhakor's* publication, there were only a handful of Bengali newspapers; their numbers totalled six, and none was a daily. *Probhakor* became the first vernacular daily of India, as Bankim points out (710, 712).

Following Jogendramohan's death in the Bengali Year 1239, *Probhakor* ceased its publication, only to reappear in 1243, this time also under the patronage of the Thakurs of Pathuriaghata (Bankim 711). Clearly, the crowd-on-the-street hypothesis of Rosinka Chaudhuri does not hold much ground. Upon a close inspection of the history of *Probhakor* and Gupta, we can see that Gupta and his newspaper thrived on the patronage of the rich, as an extensively long list of its wealthy patrons published by Gupta and quoted by Bankim establishes beyond doubt (712). The list contains a total of twenty two names, including some of the crème de la crème of the wealthy and powerful Bengalis of Kolkata. Gupta once told his brother (who showed some indifference to work and salary, and did not take professional responsibilities seriously): “If I go on begging for one day, from this Kolkata city alone I can fetch one lakh rupees. What will befall you (when I am no more)?” (Bankim 715). This shows the extent of Gupta's influence over his rich patrons.

This is not to say that Gupta or *Shongbād Probhākor* did not enjoy popular support of the common readers. They surely did. In fact Gupta's project of coordination necessarily depended on an alliance of different interests, different classes and different sensibilities. He freely moved across the boundaries which separated these different zones because here was a language at his service that was yet to be split between the high and the low, here was an indigenous ethos that was still commonly shared: “Ishwar Gupta lived at the crossroad of the old and the new. Just like the new times, he took membership of a number of societies including Brahma Samaj, and just like the old times, Gupta used to compose for *Kobi* troupes and half-*Ākhrāi*” (Bankim 713). In other words, Gupta effortlessly walked to and fro across the line between new and old sensibilities, he was open to the new while firmly rooted in his old cultural traditions. Sadly, the new would not show the same openness to the old and very soon the old would be discarded as obscure and obscene. Bankim recollects that there took place a severe *Kobir Lorai* (albeit one that was in printed format), between Ishwar Gupta and Gourishankar Bhattacharya, editor of

Roshoraj. There was 'high obscenity' from both sides in this battle, which was finally won by Gupta. James Long campaigned for an anti-obscenity law in the aftermath of this sensational incident. Following the enactment of this law Bengali literature was purged off this sin of obscenity, as Bankim observes (713).

A core concern of Gupta's project of coordination was to consolidate the Bengalis living in different geographical locations, in different parts of Bengal and India. He tried to accomplish this mission with his daily, where he used to publish accounts of different districts of Bengal, facilitated by his extensive travels in these districts. Gupta used to travel by boat after Durgapujo, as Bankim tells us; he tried to excavate Bengal's history as he tried to map Bengali culture through these travels. Upon touring east Bengal, he wrote a poem about Raja Rajballabh; he wrote on the ruins of Gour, the ancient capital of Bengal (Bankim 714). Thus, Gupta was turning his Kolkata daily into a worthy vehicle of Bengali nation-consciousness, as Kolkata was justifying itself as the epicentre of Bengali identity. Consolidation of the Bengali community was being spearheaded from Kolkata, the seat of Bengali revival.

Chandpal Ghat on the Ganges. James Baillie Fraser, 1814.

In Bankim this revival comes to be self-conscious of its deflection from its indigenous coordinates: “Obscenity is a major fault in Ishwar Gupta's poetry. By omitting that (obscenity), in order to bowdlerize (Bankim uses the word 'bowdlerize' in his Bengali essay on Gupta) Ishwar Gupta, we have made his poetry powerless. The true connoisseur of poetry will decry us.” (718-719). Bankim proceeds to observe that Ishwar Gupta's obscenity is not really obscenity after all, because his is an anger against

falsehood and sin. This point is repeatedly emphasised by Bankim throughout his essay on Gupta: that Ishwar Gupta was an enemy of falsehood: “The sages used such language. For the Bengalis of those days such a language was habitual. I have seen many such instances, where veteran, noble-souled, sober, civil, honest people have started using foul language by looking at a sinful crime. The language to express anger in those days was obscene itself.” (719). Bankim insists that Gupta does not resort to obscene language for sensual, selfish gratifications, but with the purpose to give vent to his ire. This defence by Bankim is purported to save Ishwar Gupta from being castigated by an increasingly prudish age, under the heavy influence of Victorian morality. Further, Bankim is also quick to point out that the question of taste varies across time, and across space, and varies from one country to another (719). Caution therefore had to be exercised by those educated Bengalis who were bearers of Victorian sensibility before summarily dismissing Ishwar Gupta. Thus a thorough but veiled defence of Gupta's obscenity comes from Bankim, who challenges the imperial codes penalising Gupta's obscenity. Bankim pithily comments: “Many ancient poets of our country after being caught by the law of British taste have been convicted of the crime of obscenity for no guilt of their own” (720).

Nation-consciousness attempts to fight back deflection, as Bankim defends Ishwar Gupta. However as the terms of that defence also had to be colonially approved, conforming to the dominant colonial standards, the resultant circuit of forces becomes rather complex. Bankim in any case did a commendable job, he did the best he could do, given the tide of those times. Bankim spoke of Ishwar Gupta as a prophet who was ahead of his times: “Ishwar Gupta was much larger than his poetry. His real identity is not there in his poetry. Those who are specially talented very often are ahead of their times. Ishwar Gupta was ahead of his time” (723). It is interesting to note that Bankim here probably alludes to Gupta's prose, most likely his journalistic writing, as greater than his poetry. It's clear that Gupta's poetry remained decisively passé for the new sensibility of the *new* nineteenth century, whereas Gupta belonged to the *old* nineteenth century. However, Bankim cites three cases of Gupta's pioneering role.

First, patriotism. Bankim is not sure whether it ever existed among the Bengalis of previous eras, but he notes that it was really rare at the time of Gupta, and here Bankim quotes from Gupta's celebrated poem *Swadesh* (*Shodesh*). Bankim begins his essay with an anecdote where a Bengali after newly acquiring the status of a *Shaheb* (a westernised gentleman) cannot understand what *mocha* (plantain flower) is, and after much trouble decides to call it *kela ka phool* (flower of banana, in Hindustani, which was a lingua franca of Raj administration). Bankim says that while majority of Bengalis are being

westernised these days (and therefore joining the *kela-ka-phool* bandwagon), Ishwar Gupta sticks to the Bengali *mocha* (706). There is also one personal experience which Bankim shares in order to explain the importance of Gupta to Bengali nation-consciousness. Bankim recounts an experience of enjoying a moonlit night by the Ganges, when he was looking for an apt poetic expression which would correspond with the scenery. He found none in English, and he could not find any such expression in modern Bengali poets like Madhusudan, Nabinchandra and Hemchandra. Then he heard a song of a boatman from afar: “Only this desire is there in my mind, mother/ By uttering Durga, I give up this life on Ganges”. Upon hearing that, Bankim animatedly felt: “Then my soul got quenched, the tune of my mind was there, could hear the heart's desire of a Bengali in the Bengali language” (706). Bankim observed that here was an element of identification, here someone could identify with one's own land, one's own locale, one's own roots, which was not to be found in the recent Bengali literature which was under heavy western influence, which was 'sophisticated' (again by colonial standards), but was certainly uprooted. “That is why I have attempted to collect Ishwar Gupta's Poetry. Here everything is purely Bengali. Madhusudan, Hemchandra, Nabinchandra, Rabindranath are poets of the educated Bengalis. Ishwar Gupta is a poet of the Bengalis. Nowadays pure Bengali poets are no longer born – there is no scope for that – there is no use for that. Unless the condition of Bengal deteriorates, a pure Bengali poet cannot once more be born” (Bankim 706).

The second aspect of Gupta's pioneering role was his attitude to religion. Ishwar Gupta's religious views were ahead of his times, and here Bankim shares this startling information with us that at one point of time Ishwar Gupta was a Brahmo (706). Gupta was a part of Adi Brahmo Shomaj, and was a member of Tottobodhini Shobha; he used to worship together with Brahmos and used to give speeches in Brahmo meetings. He was close to and admired by Debendranath Thakur, as Bankim informs us. The third aspect was Ishwar Gupta's politics. Bankim comments that Gupta's political view was quite generous (Bankim uses the word 'udar' which can also mean liberal), and in this too he was ahead of his time (706). Unfortunately, owing to his space constraints Bankim does not discuss this point any further.

Bankim is quite correctly aware of the geocultural significance of Gupta's accounts of his travels in the districts of Bengal. What I call Gupta's project of coordiNation in this article is most strategically executed in this part of Gupta's career. Gupta travelled through the Rajshahi district of east Bengal on boat along the river Padma, and his travelogue is published under the heading “Bhromonkari Bondhur Potro” (A Travelling Friend's Letter) (1: 211ff).

View of Kidderpore from the opposite bank of Ganges. James Baillie Fraser 1826.

He talks about the significant people whom he personally met there, about local schools and institutions, the history of which he came to know. He is aware of amusing and idiosyncratic anecdotes and shares them. He introduces some major figures of local importance who constitute the upper echelons of Bengali society in the district. From Rajshahi Gupta travels to Pabna, as leaving the river Padma he sails on Ichamoti river (1: 217ff). His itinerary closely reflects the cultural geography of Bengalis, always a riverine people. Gupta fearlessly criticises the indigo planters who oppress farmers and the complicity of the local British administrator in that act of oppression, offers a demographical sketch of the district and tells us about its administrative structure and division into *thanas*, provides a thorough list of all the *Jomidars* of this district, briefly describes its creation in 1828 by eking out some of the areas of Rajshahi and Jessore, and expresses his grief that the high officials (all British) of the district have not learnt Bengali well enough, which acts as an impediment in governance.

This should be noted here that Ishwar Gupta used *Shongbād Probhākor* as a vehicle of protest against the severe oppressions of the colonial indigo planters, and an otherwise hostile anthologist Swapan Basu (he is adverse to Ishwar Gupta for siding with the British against the revolutionary movement of the Santhals, instead of expressing a solidarity with the latter (1: 43); Basu is highly anachronistic in expecting an expression of revolutionary solidarity from Gupta towards the Santhals, we might say that he is judging Ishwar Gupta by his an unfair yardstick) showers high words of praise on Gupta for fearlessly writing against this oppression on the Bengali farmers carried out by the white

colonisers. Since the inception of *Shongbād Probhākor* in the 1830s Gupta's newspaper took up a fearless stand in favour of Bengali farmers who were oppressed by indigo planters, and Gupta did not stop writing against the colonial atrocities committed in Bengal's villages by the indigo planters till the end of his life; even after his death, *Probhakor* remained faithful to the editorial line set by Ishwar Gupta, and continued to give detailed coverage on the atrocities of indigo Planters, even at the risk of legal-governmental actions (Basu: 1: 50). Basu's collection also establishes that *Probhakor* criticised not just the white non-governmental settlers who imposed indigo planting in one village after another, but the British magistrates were also exposed in Gupta's daily (1: 330).

Let us go back to Gupta's travels in districts. The next region in his itinerary was Faridpur, and Ishwar Gupta gave a detailed account of this area, including its demography, its cultural life and its institutions. An account of Dhaka College follows (one notices that not a single Muslim is found among the scholarship holding students – though the community held a demographic majority in this area – the complete list of whom is given by Gupta) (1: 231ff), and then an account of the district Bhulua is given where Gupta talks at length about its natural and human geography (1: 234ff). Gupta repeatedly observes that the caste hierarchy of east Bengal (Bhulua and Chittagong in particular) is at variance with the system prevalent in west Bengal (1: 237, 241, 248, 263). A description of Chittagong follows next, and then Gupta takes up Tripura, Coomilla and Bikrampur. He discusses about Rajnagar at length, the capital of Raja Rajballabh, and mentions the Raja's praiseworthy attempt to initiate widow marriage (1: 263ff). Next, Gupta turns to Barisal. He notices that Barisal has a total of 1 million population, out of which majority is Hindu (*dosh ana*, or 10/16th as he puts it) (1: 268), but he also notices that among the Muslims the Firajis (adherents of Faraizi movement, started by Haji Shariyatullah) are gaining momentum. Firajis are extremely tyrannical and aggressive, Gupta observes (1: 277). A word or two about this movement (with close links with Wahabi) may not be out of place here. Founded in 1818, this movement wanted to purge all Hindu impurities from Islam in Bengal. It insisted on adherence to proper Islamic codes, and aggressively propagated Islam, subjecting non-believers (i.e. Hindus) and deviants (who were Muslims but were not following proper Islam; for Faraizis they were deviants) to violence. Probably the Faraizi movement played a key role in changing the demographic composition of Barisal and other districts of east Bengal, by slowly making them Muslim majority areas. This is a trajectory of Bengal's modern history which needs to be explored in details. Gupta's merit was that he was able to bring the worrying feature of the Faraizi movement to the notice of Kolkata intelligentsia.

But his was just a cursory glance at that phenomenon which would consequently prove fatal for the Bengali speaking Hindus in the next hundred years. Gupta did not certainly foresee that.

With Barisal his travelling commentary on east Bengal districts comes to an end, in which Gupta has offered objective portraits of folk life that was vanishing fast in the wake of colonialism. His itinerant project of writing about east Bengal qualifies as our first cultural documentation. However, it is not without flaws. Gupta sometimes appears to patronise rural life which can amount to condescension. Needless to say, a big brother attitude of Kolkata does not help coordination. But to his credit, Gupta has an open mind, and a curiosity worthy of a cultural historian which together inform his attempt to document the socio-cultural life of the districts. Gupta consolidates Bengali nation-consciousness with Kolkata as its worthy epicentre, as the purveyor of Bengali territories, coordinating among its peripheries. Modern day Bengalis become part of a coordinating system with Kolkata as their heart and as their nerve centre, ensuring that a network is maintained and information from different parts are duly received and processed inside a new discourse of nation-consciousness. Thus a sense of a common Bengali community is forged through *Shongbād Probhākor*.

Probhākor became a name. So, exploiting its brand name, Gupta later authored a book named *Hit Probhākor* which as a text mixed poetry with prose, touching upon God and the human relationship with God, but here the focus was really on the ethical questions of existence meant for young minds, in the vein of classical Indian texts like *Panchatantra* and *Hitopadesha*. But this book also contained a number of banalities, like the advice for dispensing with a bad wife, an arrogant servant and a crooked friend (*Collected Works* 2: 34). This book has four chapters: *Mitrolabh*, *Shuhridbhed*, *Bigroho* and *Shondhi* which closely parallels the textual scheme of *Panchatantra*. Significantly, this book was written upon a request from Bethune, who wanted Ishwar Gupta to produce a book of Bengali verse for school going children, as Ishwar Gupta's brother Ramchandra informed in the preface to this posthumously published text, where he attached the original letter from Bethune and its translation in Bengali (*Collected Works* 2: 2-4). Here it is quite amusing to note that Ishwar Gupta himself lampooned Bethune in one of his satirical poems that spewed venom against female education initiated by Bethune, who alone had destroyed the traditional virtues in women (like those of keeping *brotos*, which were rituals involving folk worship in different seasons of the year; there were chants in Bengali and a fast had to be maintained till the worship was over) in his zeal to impart Western education on Bengali girls, according to Gupta (1: ২৭৭(৯)).² Extract from that satirical piece is provided in the notes.

But *Shongbād Probhākor* supported the demand for education for girls throughout 1840s and 1850s, it supported widow marriage, and opposed *Kulinism* (that encouraged polygamy which in turn could be a bane for all Bengali women, not necessarily the women of the three upper castes – Brahman, Vaidya and Kayastha – alone where *Kulinism* was prominent), as Swapan Basu (who is otherwise very highly critical of Ishwar Gupta, as we have already noted) tells us (1: 8). Ishwar Gupta himself participated the first meeting of the governors of the first all girls' school in Kolkata founded upon the initiative of Bethune, named Victoria *Balika Biddaloy* (later rechristened on Bethune himself after his untimely death), as a report in *Shongbād Probhākor* dated 25 May 1849 tells us, extracted in Basu (2: 273-274); in another report published in the same year on 24 July, Gupta's newspaper exhorts all stakeholders to come forward for the noble cause of female education, and particularly criticises the Brahmos for their inaction in this front: this is also available in Basu's anthology (2: 277). *Probhākor* continued the editorial policy of Gupta and continued to support the cause of girls' education, which is evident in another report published in 1879 (Basu: 2: 329).

So, is there a dichotomy in Gupta then? Does he both support and oppose female education? Having himself authored *brotokotha* or ritual chants for the worship of Shubochoni and Shottonarayan, Gupta as an ardent supporter of these *brotos* might have been offended that in the western-style education girls were encouraged to treat such indigenous rituals as little more than superstition. Importantly, his nostalgia for the vanishing culture of *brotos* seems to be shared by others as well. For example, a magazine named *Deepika* lamenting for the steady loss of the culture of *broto* among Kolkata women in its issue published in the Bengali Year 1294, quotes those lines of Ishwar Gupta which precisely speaks of the loss of the culture of observing *broto* in women; this issue of *Deepika* is collected in Swapan Basu's anthology of nineteenth century Bengali periodicals (2: 127).

Gupta was not a misogynist, as it is sometimes made out to be, after Bankim in his essay made some adverse comments about Gupta, regarding the lack of a soothing feminine presence in his life, which, according to Bankim, suppressed Gupta's ability to sympathise with the fairer sex (710). Gupta in fact encouraged women writers and correspondents, by publishing their writings in *Probhākor*, this is evident in the case of Thakurani Dasi, a forgotten writer who used to publish her columns in Gupta's newspaper (Basu 2: 701). Surely his editorial policy was not misogynist. Further, Gupta's *Probhākor* was a staunch supporter of Rani Rashmoni, and publicised her different welfare activities (one report dated 14 March 1853 is about the Rani's contribution towards building up civic amenities and urban

infrastructure including roads, sanitation, drinking water and building of ghats), printed her appeal against rampant polygamy of *Kulinism* (report dated 31 July 1856), as well as her initiative for revival of Bengal's Hinduism which took a concrete embodiment in the Dokkhineshshor Kali Temple (report dated 12 April 1856, and here we must note that the Rani faced a lot of hostilities from conservative Hindus because of her lowly status in the Brahminical caste hierarchy as she was a Mahishsho/Māhiṣya by caste, and was not considered to be eligible to build a temple, and therefore the stand of *Probhakor* vis-a-vis the Rani is anything but a conservative, reactionary Hindu stand); *Probhakor* also reports in pithy details about the drunken raid of a band of armed Britishers (a hundred in number) upon the residence of Rani Rashmoni (dated 6 May 1858), a report that created a stir among the Hindus of Kolkata (Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay: 2: 743-744). Looking at Ishwar Gupta's admiration for the Rani, it is quite hard to believe that he was not able to respect women, as Bankim suggests.

Rani Rashmoni

However, those apparently misogynist lines of Gupta which lampooned the western-style education for girls are oft quoted by progressive critics inevitably to brandish a sword against Gupta, but indeed what we see here is a prophetic statement; education *on colonial terms* spelt a disaster for the indigenous culture of Bengal. One easy proof of that would be to ask those who regularly parade this piece of Gupta's poem as a specimen of conservative Hindu misogyny that how many of them know anything at all about the *broto* of *Shanj Shenjoti* (সাঁজ সঁজোতি), which in Gupta's poem is cited as one of the lost traditions.

In fact, the present writer looked up Abanindranath Thakur's *Banglar Broto* in search of the *broto* of *Shanj Shenjoti*, to no avail. After looking up internet, a number of sites (almost all of them from Bangladesh) told us that this *broto* probably originated among the Oraon tribe who still practise it, and that *Shenjoti/Shejuti* rituals are held in the late autumn month of *Oghran/AgraHaayana*,³ while a page devoted to the district of Faridpur in Bangladesh mentions this *broto* in a cursory manner among other

*broto*s which, we are told, are still practised by the villagers of this district.⁴

Finally, a full transcript of the ritual chants of this *broto* of *Shanj Shenjoti* was found in Dakshinaranjan Mitra Majumdar's *Thandidir Thole- Banglar Brotokotha* which forms a part of the first volume of his *Collected Works* (355-364).

Gupta's support of and opposition to female education therefore form a core dilemma of nation-consciousness, that keeps on pushing its trajectory in two opposite directions: collaboration and resistance, social reform and social reaction, imperial Enlightenment and native tradition. And they were sometimes held together, albeit in a great tension. *Hit Probhakor* is meant for imparting a lesson in Bengali poetics as well as classical Indian ethics, but this book can also be considered as a product of the school education system introduced by British. A newsreport of 1839 collected in Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay's anthology attests Gupta's long term interest in the spread of liberal school education, while he participated in the foundation meeting of a school at Barasat (2: 71-72). Clearly, Gupta and others saw a potential in the western-style education as it was seen to be accommodative of Hindu interests, though it is equally true that clashes were also frequent. Hindu College authorities once deliberated on the option of prosecuting Gupta because of his comments against the college, we are told in Bhabatosh Dutta's introduction to *Ishwar Gupta Rochito Kobijiboni*, and the same source also tells us that Gupta translated Tom Paine's *Age of Reason* into Bengali as a counter-ballast against Christian missionaries, on behalf of a conservative Hindu association named *Dhormoshobha* (||o). In this period, the strange transaction between the Hindu interests and the Western interests was in its full-fledged form, and it produced some fruitful manoeuvres where the Hindu was able to produce his own ideological discourse provided that it did not immediately collide with the interests of colonialism. Kolkata of nineteenth century is all about this strategic and strange marriage of convenience between the occident and the orient. It involves a deferral of the nation-consciousness, the way the end of Bankim's *Anandamath* involves a deferral of Hindu self-rule in favour of immediate British colonisation. Kolkata would gladly remain a colonial city in this precise gesture of deferral, singing the praise of the British empire, provided the empire offered the space necessary for the Bengali Babus to stage a Renaissance. This deferral of nation-consciousness is archetypically exhibited by the nineteenth century Kolkata which was Ishwar Gupta's world, as his life and works symbolise the deferred movement of Bengali identity. Some of Gupta's poems containing praises for the British empire are produced in the notes.⁵

The concepts of nationalism and patriotism were undoubtedly influenced by an exposure to the west, though this is a simplification to say that notions of a coherent Bengaliness did not exist prior to the arrival of British. But it is indeed true that poems like *Shodesh* (*Swadesh*) speak of a nationalist fervour which was perhaps absent in the poetry of previous ages (translation of a part of this poem done by me is provided in the notes). Again, Gupta's poem 'Matribhasha' (2: 441) is a case in point. The very phrase of 'mother tongue' was brought about by colonialism, and Gupta's use of the phrase *matribhasha* is a straight translation of the phrase mother tongue. What deflected nation-consciousness also helped to produce nation-consciousness by a dialectical process, and we can think of this as a *pearl-oyster model* of the birth of nation-consciousness, where the trauma of imperialism produces the pearl of nation-consciousness. It was a composite phenomenon.

Nineteenth century Kolkata was a composite event, and it was taking place not just right in front of Ishwar Gupta's eyes, this event was happening with Ishwar Gupta performing *in* it. Old was giving way to the new, but was leaving nevertheless its ineluctable imprints. The *Kobiwalas* of Gupta's chronicle were breathing their last as Gupta was growing up in this city. Horu Thakur of Shimulia died in 1824, and Nilu Thakur (also of Shimulia) died in 1825, as the obituaries in *Shomachar Dorpon* tells us, collected in Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay's anthology of early nineteenth century periodicals (1: 143). If one needed to write an obituary for Ishwar Gupta, it should have mentioned him as a collaborator of colonialism and a sad victim of the same, as a leader of the cultural resistance movement of his people against colonial aggression, as a forgotten Brahmo who remained a traditional Hindu all the way to his core, as a reformer who sometimes was trapped in reaction, as an important turn in the time-space curve of Bengali nation-consciousness which he helped to both grow courageously and grovel abominably in front of the British eyes. He was born a *Boddi*, considered to be the archetypically *intelligent* caste among Bengalis – indeed, he is referred to in one of the contemporary rival periodicals as “Ishshor Boddi” in a slightly contemptuous tone (Brajendranath Bandyopadhyay 2: 186) – and he was *uneducated*, and yet before he was twenty he became editor of a newspaper that was about to become the first vernacular daily in the Indian subcontinent. He became a renowned poet while still in his adolescence, he became our first cultural historian and chronicled the lives and works of *Kobiwalas*. His people had a glorious history of cultural performance, which was becoming obscure very fast, and he anxiously wanted to rescue that history. He coordinated Bengaliness in the best possible way that he could do in those circumstances and by the time he died at the premature age of 47 in 1859, he came to be seen as the grand

patriarch of Bengali art and letters. In childhood he was a prodigy, in adolescence he was an uneducated poet-songmaker, in youth he was an establishment, and in death he is a misunderstood figure. *He is nineteenth century Kolkata crying out to be reread.*

A clipping from a youtube video which laments that Ishwar Gupta's birthplace at Kanchrapara lies neglected and forgotten.

Curiously, the heading of this report in this image introduces Gupta as an “eminent journalist”

(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x44vbT6YCAg>)

Notes:

1. Here is a translation of a part of that poem of Ishwar Gupta done by me, where he exhorts his countrymen to embrace a native dog, forsaking *the* foreign God:

যত কালের যুবো যেন সুবো

ইংরেজি কয় বাঁকা ভাবে।

ধোরে গুরু পুরুত মারে জুতো

ভিখারী কি অন্ন পাবে?

আগে মেয়ে গুলো ছিল ভালো

ব্রত ধর্ম কোর্তো সবে।

একা বেথুন এসে শেষ করেছে

আর কি তাদের তেমন পাবে?

যত ছুঁড়ীগুলো তুড়ী মেরে

কেতাব হাতে নিষ্চে যবে।

তখন এ. বি. শিখে বিবি সেজে

বিলাতী বোল কবেই কবে।।

এখন আর কি তারা সাজি নিয়ে

সাঁজ সঁজোতির ব্রত গাবে?

সব কাঁটা চামচে ধোরবে শেষে

পিঁড়ি পেতে আর কি থাকে?

ও ভাই, আর কিছুদিন বেঁচে থাকলে,

পাবেই পাবেই দেখতে পাবে।

এরা আপন হাতে হাঁকিয়ে বগী

গড়ের মাঠে হাওয়া খাবে।

আছে গোটা কতক বুড়ো য দিন
 ত দিন কিছু রক্ষা পাবে।
 ও ভাই, তারা হলেই দফা রক্ষা
 এককালে সব ফুরিয়ে যাবে।

(*Collected Works 1: এগারো-বারো*)

In this poem Gupta laments about the loss of the traditional virtues of women and in a sudden flourish of dystopic misogyny shudders at the prospect of Bengali women becoming masters of their own fate like the white European women after being subjected to western-style education, becoming independent, themselves driving horse-drawn carriages to enjoy the evening air of Maidan. It is not necessary to translate the whole poem. As it is impossible to translate Gupta's wonderful rhymes in Bengali, there is little use in translating his anti-feminism alone. In this connection, it may be pertinent to quote from Mousumi Dasgupta's review article from the inaugural issue of JBS:

Fakir Mohan Senapati, considered the father of Oriya nationalism, once commented that Oriya language survived the onslaught of Turk-Afghan-Persian-Arabic influences because of the domestic sphere that was dominated by “Gruhalakshmis” who resisted the foreign influence that had the men under its sway (since they worked in close contact with the Islamic colonizers and used a language and adopted a culture that celebrated this collaboration) as Esha Dey, noted Bengali writer recently reminisced in a personal conversation with the editor of JBS. Women's role in sustaining the indigenous culture and language within domestic spheres has every claim to be a topic of critical study. Women were less prone to foreign influences and they played crucial roles in celebrating cultural expressions of identity

However, the male fantasy of women's purity contributes heavily to this image. It was certainly no glory of the Indians that women had to be confined within the boundaries of her home (as some nationalists uncritically assumed), and yet we see that women's confinement became a matter of glory

for patriarchy, and the nationalists of the old school. Women as prized possession of patriarchy and women as unspoilt, pure, innocent space (free from all polluting and corrupting foreign influences) meant for the furtherance of the *ancien regime* are the two fancies which come together in this celebration of women as the sustainers of lost treasures.

("Motherhood/Maidenhood in Revolutionary Nationalism", JBS 1.1, 2012, p 151-52)

3. <<http://onushilon.org/geography/bangladesh/khudro-nrigosthi/orao/orao.htm>>. Accessed on 17 Sep 2014.

4. <<http://greaterfaridpur.info/index.php?option=content&value=347>>. Accessed on 17 Sep 2014.

5. Some extracts from Gupta's overtly collaborationist poems are provided here, where he sings the praise of the British empire and lampoons the rebels of 1857 war of independence.

ধন্য চিফ্ কমাণ্ডার ধন্য দেও গড়ে

গণ্য বটে সৈন্যগণ ধন্য দেও তায়।

লর্ডের রহিল মান গডের কুপায়।।

সদয় সমরকল্পে বিভূ দয়াময়।

... জয় ব্রিটিশের জয় রণে ব্রিটিশের জয়।।

পেটে খেলে পিঠে সয় এই বাক্য ধর।

রাজার সাহায্যেহেতু রণসজ্জা পর।।

নানা পাপে পটু নানা নাকি গুণে, না ,না।

অধর্মের অন্ধকারে হইয়াছে কাণা।।

ভাল-দোষে ভাল তুমি ঘটালে প্রমাদ।

আগেতে দেখেছ ঘুঘু, শেষে দেখ ফাঁদ।।

পিঁপীড়া ধরেছে ডানা মরিবার তরে।

হ্যাদে কি শুনি বানী?

হ্যাদে কি শুনি বানী ঝাঙ্গির রানী

ঠোঁটকাটা কাকী।।

মেয়ে হয়ে সেনা নিয়ে সাজিয়াছে নাকি?

নানা তার ঘরের টেঁকি

নানা তার ঘরের টেঁকি মাগী খেঁকী

গোয়ালের দলে।

এতদিনে ধনে জনে যাবে রসাতলে।। (*Collected Works 1: পনেরো*)

পড়ুক বিপক্ষদল মনের অনলে

উড়ুক ব্রিটিশ ধ্বজা সমুদয় স্থলে।।

ইংরাজের পরাক্রম রবির প্রকাশ।

অত্যাচার-অন্ধকার হইল বিনাশ।।

ব্রিটিশের জয় জয় বল সবে ভাই রে।

এসো সবে নেচে কুঁদে বিভূষণ গাই রে।। (*Collected Works 1: ষোল*)

All of these poems are written on the occasion of the victory of the British in 1857, which is divinely ordained for Gupta. Clearly Gupta reflects the dominant feeling of euphoria among the educated Bengalis who constituted the backbone of British civil administration throughout India. Gupta freely uses English words like “Lord” and “God” in his Bengali poems in order to create an atmosphere of loyalty. Again, there is no use in translating whole pieces,. Interestingly, Gupta's dyspeptic lampooning of Rani Jhansi (Gupta does not spare Nana Sahib as well) has a distinct feel of *Pāñchālī*, as it uses refrains and metres and rhythms suitable for this genre. One can almost visualise Gupta's poems being sung by some performer of *Pāñchālī* after British victory in 1857, before this indigenous art form finally went extinct.

Primary Bibliography

Gupta, Ishwarchandra. *Ishwar Gupta Rochonaboli (Collected Works) Volume 1 & Volume 2*. Ed. Shantikumar Dasgupta and Haribandhu Mukhoti. Foreword (to both vols) by Tripurashankar Senshastri. Kolkata: DuttaChowdhuri and Sons, 1361 (Bengali Year).

---. *Ishwarchandra Gupta Rochito Kobijoboni*. Ed. Bhabatosh Dutta. Kolkata: Calcutta Book House, 1365 (Bengali Year). Note: The preliminary pages of this book use anna (erstwhile constituent of rupee) symbols as page numbers, and while citing from this book's introduction written by Dutta, closest available symbols have been used.

Secondary Bibliography

Anderson, Benedict. *Imagined Communities*. London: Verso, 2006.

Bandyopadhyay, Brajendranath. *Shongbadpotre Shekaler Kotha, Vol. 1*. Kolkata: Bongiyō Shahitto Porishot, 1415 (Bengali Year).

---. *Shongbadpotre Shekaler Kotha, Vol. 2*. Kolkata: Bongiyō Shahitto Porishot, 1401 (Bengali Year).

- Bandyopadhyay, Nachiketa. "Hungry Movement after 50 Years." *Journal of Bengali Studies* 3.1 (2014). 189-204.
- Basu, Swapan, ed. *Shongbad Shamoyikpotre Unish Shotoker BaNalishomaj (A Selection of News and Articles from 19th Century Journals), Vol 1 (2nd Edition)*. Kolkata: Poshchimbongo Bangla Academy, 2013.
- . *Shongbad Shamoyikpotre Unish Shotoker BaNalishomaj (A Selection of News and Articles from 19th Century Journals), Vol 2*. Kolkata: Poshchimbongo Bangla Academy, 2003.
- Bhattacharya, Amitrasudan. *Probondho Ponchashot: Bishoy Bankimchandra*. Kolkata: Protibhash, 2014.
- Chattopadhyay, Bankim Chandra. *Bankim Rochonaboli, Volume 2*. Kolkata: Reflect, 1999.
- . *Rajmohan's Wife*. New Delhi: Penguin, 2009.
- Chaudhuri, Nirad C. *Autobiography of an Unknown Indian (Vol. 1)*. Mumbai: Jaico Publishing House, 2013.
- Chaudhuri, Rosinka. "Poet of the Present: The Material Object in the World of Iswar Gupta." *New Cultural Histories of India: Materiality and Practices*. Eds. Partha Chatterje, Tapati Guha-Thakurta and Bodhisattva Kar. New Delhi: OUP, 2014. 87-112.
- Dey, Purnachandra Udbhatsagar. *Kobi Anthony Shaheb*. Kolkata: Shoptorshi, 2013.
- Dutt, Romesh Chunder. *The Literature of Bengal*. Calcutta: Thacker Spink, 1895.
- Dutt, Utpal. *Girish Manosh*. Kolkata: M C Sarkar, 1994.
- Gupta, Bipin Bihari. *Puraton Proshongo*. Ed. Asit Bandyopadhyay. Kolkata: Pustok Biponi, 1989.
- Hunt, Tristram. *Ten Cities that Made an Empire*. London: Allen Lane, 2014.
- Husain, S. Mahdi. *Bahadur Shah Zafar and the War of 1857 in Delhi*. Delhi: Aakar, 2006.
- Joshi, Priti. "1857: Or, Can the Indian 'Mutiny' Be Fixed?". [branchcollective.org](http://www.branchcollective.org/?ps_articles=priti-joshi-1857-or-can-the-indian-mutiny-be-fixed). Accessed on 17 Sept. 2014. <http://www.branchcollective.org/?ps_articles=priti-joshi-1857-or-can-the-indian-mutiny-be-fixed>. Web.
- Mallick, Pramathanath. *Kolikatar Kotha (Aadikando)*. Kolkata: Pustok Biponi, 2001.
- Mitra Majumdar, Dakshinaranjan. *Dokkhinaronjon Rochonashomogro Vol.1*. Kolkata: Mitra and Ghosh, 1419 (Bengali Year).
- Patrea, Purnendu. *Purono Kolkatar Kothachitro*. Kolkata: Dey's, 2005.
- Ray, Kalidas. *Prachin Bongo Shahitto*. Kolkata: Aparna, 2008.

Roy, Dilipkumar. *Rochonashongroho (Vol. 3)*. Ed. Ujjwalkumar Majumdar. Kolkata: Ananda, 2005.

Sarkar, Sumit. "Vidyasagar and Brahmanical Society". *Women and Social Reform in Modern India: A Reader*. Ed. Sumit Sarkar and Tanika Sarkar. Indiana: Indiana University Press, 2008. 118-145.

Srijato. facebook.com page. Post dated 22 December 2012. Accessed on 17 September 2014.

<<https://www.facebook.com/songisrijato/photos/pb.341860289254994.-2207520000.1413930761./341868385920851/?type=3&theater>>. Web.

Suman, Kabir. facebook.com profile. Post/ status update dated 17 April 2014. Accessed on 17 April 2014. Web.

Thakur, Abanindranath. *Banglar Broto*. Kolkata: Gangchil, 2013.

(All translations from Bengali which appear in this article, unless quoted from another critic, are done by the author. All Bengali words, apart from familiar proper nouns, are spelt according to Bengali standard of pronunciation)

Tamal Dasgupta is the founder editor of Journal of Bengali Studies and Assistant Professor of English, Bhim Rao Ambedkar College, University of Delhi, Delhi, India.